

Optimization of hybrid sensible-latent seasonal heat storage systems

William Delgado-Díaz^{a, b} , Marcel Troxler^a, Ruben Hijwegen^a,
 Reto Hendry^a ,
 Sophia Haussener^b

^a Competence Center Thermal Energy Storage, Lucerne University of Applied Sciences and Arts (HSLU), Technikumstrasse 21, Horw, 6048, Switzerland

^b Laboratory of Renewable Energy Science and Engineering, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne (EPFL), Rte Cantonale, Lausanne, 1015, Switzerland

^c Cowa Thermal Solutions AG, Technopark Luzern Platz 4, Root, 6039, Switzerland

HIGHLIGHTS

- Developed a multi-objective optimization framework for hybrid sensible-latent heat storage systems in multi-family residential buildings.
- The system model comprises photovoltaic (PV) panels, a heat pump (HP) and thermal energy storage (TES) and optimizes for thermal self-sufficiency, cost, and environmental impact.
- A 70 % thermal self-sufficiency was identified as the optimal point, balancing Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH) and Global Warming Potential (GWP).
- Systems achieving thermal self-sufficiency up to 85 % are technically feasible but result in higher costs, storage volumes and comparable GWP to the oil boiler base case.
- Future advancements in Phase Change Material (PCM) technology and decreasing PV costs could further lower costs and improve integration and sustainability.

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hybrid sensible-latent thermal energy storage
 Phase change materials (PCM)
 Seasonal thermal energy storage (STES)
 Levelized cost of heat (LCOH)
 Global warming potential (GWP)

ABSTRACT

This study presents a coupled techno-economic and environmental model of hybrid sensible-latent thermal energy storage (TES) systems, integrating phase change material (PCM) macro-capsules to enhance storage capacity and performance. The multi-scale model accounts for stratification in the sensible storage and phase change dynamics in the PCM capsules. This framework is used to perform multi-objective optimization across the full range of thermal self-sufficiency (SS_{th}) levels for a multi-family building. The results show that a 70 % SS_{th} offers the optimal balance between economic feasibility and environmental impact, with a Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH) of 0.27 CHF/kWh and a Global Warming Potential (GWP) reduction of 76 % compared to fossil fuel alternatives. Systems targeting up to 85 % SS_{th} are technically feasible but come with increased costs (up to 0.33 CHF/kWh), while exceeding 85 % SS_{th} results in exponential increases in both cost and storage volume. Maximizing photovoltaic (PV) and heat pump (HP) power is critical for optimizing system performance. Future advancements in PCM technology and decreasing PV costs could lower the LCOH to 0.23 CHF/kWh and the GWP to 21 % of fossil fuel systems, demonstrating significant potential for long-term cost reductions and sustainability.

1. Introduction

The rapid global shift toward renewable energy systems has underscored the urgent need for advanced energy storage solutions capable of balancing the inherent intermittency of renewable energy generation with fluctuating demand. In particular, Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage (STES) systems, which capture surplus energy during periods of high renewable output and store it for extended durations (e.g., six

months or more), play a critical role in enhancing the efficiency and resilience of modern energy systems. Xu et al. [1] provide an extensive review of seasonal storage technologies, noting that while conventional sensible storage (using water, rock, or soil) is mature and widely implemented, latent and chemical storage methods can achieve much higher energy densities and reduced thermal losses; however, these latter methods are still largely confined to lab-scale studies and material investigations. Complementing this, Alva et al. [2] dissect the physical

* Corresponding author.

Email address: joerg.worlitschek@hslu.ch (J. Worlitschek).

Acronym			
BC	Boundary Condition	NOMAD	Nonlinear Optimization by Mesh Adaptive Direct search
BC DHW	Domestic Hot Water Boundary Condition	PCM	Phase Change Material
BC EC	Electricity Boundary Condition	PV	Photovoltaic
BC SH	Space Heating Boundary Condition	RBS	Repurposed Basement Storage (Cuboidal)
DHW	Domestic Hot Water	SAT	Sodium Acetate Trihydrate
GWP	Global Warming Potential	SHTES	Seasonal Hybrid Thermal Energy Storage
HP	Heat Pump	SIA	Swiss Society of Engineers and Architects
HWTES	Hot Water Thermal Energy Storage	SST	Spherical Storage Tank (Spherical)
LCOH	Levelized Cost of Heat	SS _{th}	Thermal Self-Sufficiency
		STES	Seasonal Thermal Energy Storage
		VIT	Vacuum Insulated Tank (Cylindrical)

properties, operational performance, and cost parameters of various TES materials, while IRENA [3] highlights on a global scale that innovation in thermal storage is pivotal for transitioning away from fossil fuels.

Large-scale field applications further validate the technical feasibility of STES. Gerschitzka et al. [4] demonstrate the development of large-volume domestic hot water storages with high insulation efficiency, directly addressing cost and scalability. Experimentally, Stropnik et al. [5] have shown that incorporating phase change materials (PCMs) into storage systems significantly enhances thermal stratification and extends the duration of usable stored energy. These benefits are corroborated by studies from Frazzica et al. [6] and Pabst et al. [7], which quantitatively compare hybrid PCM-enhanced systems with traditional water-only storages.

Integration of storage capacity with renewable energy technologies is essential for maximizing system flexibility. Yang et al. [8] review the techno-economic performance of STES and argue that coupling storage with photovoltaic (PV) panels and heat pumps (HPs) is key to mitigating renewable intermittency. Tronchin et al. [9] further contend that only an integrated approach, merging energy efficiency measures, demand-side management, and storage, can overcome the temporal mismatches between energy production and consumption. Supporting this integrated perspective, Child et al. [10] illustrate that storage technologies are indispensable for a transition to a fully renewable power sector, and Schüetz et al. [11] demonstrate that thermal storage enhances the operational flexibility of smart grids in residential heating.

Decarbonization remains a critical driver, especially in regions such as Switzerland where heating accounts for nearly 50 % of total energy consumption [12]. Fossil-fuel-based heating systems, such as oil boilers, have been reported to exhibit a Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH) of approximately 0.14 CHF/kWh and a Global Warming Potential (GWP) of around 0.32 kg CO₂ per kWh [13–15]. These high costs and environmental impacts have catalyzed policy shifts, notably Switzerland's Energy Strategy 2050, which promotes PV-assisted HP systems integrated with advanced thermal storage [15,16], as well as analyses by Greening et al. [17] and Smith et al. [18] discussing European initiatives aimed at achieving carbon-neutral building stocks by 2050.

A systems perspective is essential for fully exploiting STES potential. Sadeghi [19] argues that holistic optimization, which captures the complex interactions among energy generation, storage, and consumption, is critical. In line with this, Villasmil et al. [20] conducted an exergetic and economic optimization of STES systems, demonstrating that optimizing solar collector configurations and storage volumes can reduce required storage sizes by up to 30 % without sacrificing performance. Their subsequent work [21] further showed that variable-flow control strategies improve thermal stratification, thereby reducing both storage volume and cost. Narula et al. [22] present a simulation method that accurately captures hourly energy flows in district heating systems with seasonal storage, bridging the gap between modeling and real-world operation. Policy insights from Chiodi et al. [23] and scenario analyses by Child et al. [10] further underscore the value of bottom-up

energy system models for long-term planning, while recent assessments by Berger et al. [24] highlight the potential for integrated renewable heating solutions in residential buildings.

Advancements in PCMs have emerged as a promising route to enhance storage performance. Majumdar and Saha [25] demonstrate via numerical modeling that optimizing PCM capsule filling can boost charging efficiency by over 50 %, while Sharma et al. [26] and Teamah et al. [27] report that PCMs help maintain near-isothermal conditions during phase transitions, a crucial factor for stable operation. Sodium acetate trihydrate (SAT) based PCMs developed by Cowa Thermal Solutions AG have been selected for this study due to their commercial availability, competitive pricing, and favorable technical properties. These materials exhibit melting temperatures between 40 and 58 °C and latent heats ranging from 178 to 241 kJ/kg, characteristics that are particularly well suited for seasonal thermal energy storage applications. Recent experimental studies further substantiate the technical potential of these SAT-based PCMs. For instance, Ma et al. [28] provided a comprehensive characterization of the thermo-physical properties of sodium acetate trihydrate, developing a mathematical model of its solidification process that quantifies crystal growth rates and associated enthalpy changes during discharge. In parallel, Zhou and Xiang [29] examined the stable supercooling behavior of SAT in various container geometries, demonstrating that factors such as charging duration, cooling rate, and surface characteristics significantly influence PCM stability.

Hybrid storage solutions that combine sensible and latent heat storage are increasingly being explored to optimize both energy density and operational flexibility. Stropnik et al. [5] and Zauner et al. [30] demonstrate that embedding non-spherical, encapsulated PCM elements within a water-based storage matrix can enhance storage capacity and improve heat transfer rates. Complementary numerical studies by Ahmed et al. [31] and CFD simulations by Pabst et al. [7] reveal detailed insights into thermocline dynamics and thermal stratification in hybrid systems. Moreover, optimization studies by Wang et al. [32] and thermo-economic evaluations by Pellela et al. [33] highlight that while PCM integration improves technical performance, its high material costs often pose economic challenges. Although studies such as Bianco et al. [34] offer detailed multiscale CFD analyses for single-family systems and Hofmann et al. [35] optimize hybrid steam-PCM storage for industrial applications, these approaches remain confined to specific application domains. Their work highlights important sub-system dynamics but does not address the integrated interactions among PV, HP, and STES in residential buildings.

From a design standpoint, Del Amo et al. [36] demonstrate that increasing the size of seasonal storage can improve thermal self-sufficiency and reduce the electrical consumption of HPs; however, diminishing returns at very high self-sufficiency levels necessitate careful cost-performance balancing. Becattini et al. [37] explore hybrid compressed air energy storage integrated with TES, emphasizing that while PCM systems reduce temperature fluctuations, their capital costs remain significant. In addition, integrated system analyses by Guelpa et al. [38]

and Li et al. [39] provide a comprehensive view of life cycle impacts, and Ruesch et al. [40] point out that studies addressing the scalability and environmental impact of PCM-based solutions in buildings are still scarce.

The selection of the most relevant studies is synthesised in the Appendix (Table 11). Taken together they show two persistent gaps: almost all optimize either thermal performance or cost, but very few treat both in an integrated way, and only three attach life-cycle greenhouse-gas figures to their techno-economic results. None couples an experimentally validated hybrid sensible-latent tank with simultaneous optimisation of photovoltaic supply, heat-pump sizing and encapsulated-PCM layout under real building boundary conditions. By closing all three gaps, multi-objective optimization of LCOH, GWP and thermal self-sufficiency, validation against experimental data, and a focus on space-constrained retrofits, our study advances the state of the art beyond the best cases documented to date.

Despite the abundance of research on individual aspects of thermal storage, no study to date has delivered an experimentally validated, fully coupled system model that simultaneously captures the dynamic thermal behavior of packed-bed PCM capsules embedded in a water-based sensible storage, along with the performance of heat pumps and PV generation, while enabling large-scale multi-objective optimization. In contrast, our work makes several novel contributions. First, we introduce a PCM encapsulation and stratification model, validated against prototype experiments, that accurately captures conduction-dominated processes and realistic capsule packing geometries in a packed-bed configuration. Second, our framework employs a comprehensive multi-objective optimization strategy using the derivative-free NOMAD optimizer [41] to systematically explore a highly nonlinear parameter space, including variations in PCM shape, storage volume, and the interactions among PV, HP, and STES components. This approach allows us to simultaneously optimize economic metrics (LCOH), environmental impacts (GWP), and thermal self-sufficiency (SS_{th}). Third, by integrating detailed insights from energy system models and component perspectives, our method provides a holistic design methodology that captures the complex interactions between subsystems. By addressing both the component-level physics and the system-level integration, our study uncovers critical trade-offs among capital investment, operational efficiency, and carbon emissions, thereby offering practical design recommendations that are directly applicable to real-world, multi-family renewable heating systems. Collectively, these contributions extend the current state of the art by bridging the gap between detailed sub-system modeling and integrated, multi-objective system optimization, providing a robust framework that informs both technological development and policy planning for sustainable, cost-effective renewable heating solutions.

2. Methods

2.1. System overview

The study employs a system model developed in C++, incorporating the NOMAD optimizer (version 4.3.1) [41] along with in-house pre- and post-processing modules (see Fig. 1). The system includes a buried hybrid seasonal thermal energy storage (SHTES) unit, which uses both water and encapsulated PCM for storing excess thermal energy. Additionally, the system integrates a PV array for electricity generation, an air-source HP for thermal energy production, and an apartment building with electricity (BC EC), domestic hot water (BC DHW) and space heating (BC SH) consumption profiles further explained in Section 2.3.

The system is designed to provide both space heating (BC SH) and domestic hot water (BC DHW) for a multi-family house. A schematic representation of this system, detailing the interconnections among the various components, is provided in Fig. 1. The control logic prioritizes PV-generated electricity for electrical and heating demands, using surplus for space heating or charging the SHTES. During periods of low PV output, the SHTES provides heat, with grid electricity supplementing as

needed. The DHW service strategy involves pre-heating tap water via the SHTES and further heating in the hot water TES (HWTES) to meet temperature requirements.

The dual approach, using both a sensible (HWTES) and hybrid sensible-latent storage (SHTES), is driven by two main considerations. First, the SHTES is maintained at a lower temperature to minimize thermal losses, making it suitable for long-term storage. Second, the DHW system acts as a daily to mid-term storage solution, allowing the system to handle higher temperature and power demands separately. While latent heat storage offers a higher energy density due to the PCM used, it introduces challenges in maintaining consistent power output during discharge. This variability arises from the conduction-driven dynamics of the hybrid TES, which complicates the ability to deliver a stable power output.

Optimization parameters include dimensions and capacities of the PV system, HP, thermal storage, and PCM capsules placement. The optimization routine, guided by key performance indicators, discussed in detail in Section 2.4, seeks to minimize costs in terms of levelized cost of heat (LCOH) and global warming potential (GWP) while maximizing thermal self-sufficiency (SS_{th}) through iterative simulations. Pre-processing prepares the input data, followed by system simulations that run over multiple years. The model achieves a steady-state condition when the conditions at the start and end of a simulated year converge, ensuring stability across annual cycles. In the post-processing phase, energy flows and costs are evaluated to inform subsequent optimization cycles until the optimal solution is identified.

2.2. Numerical model

The system model includes three physical components: thermal energy storage, PV module, and HP models, complemented by boundary condition models for domestic hot water, space heating, and electricity demand. The dynamics are described by differential equations, with the PV module and HP modeled using ordinary differential equations and the thermal storage using energy conservation equations.

The thermal energy storage model, known as SolTESS, derived from the BFE project "OPTSAIS" [20], was augmented with a latent heat component and consists of three energy equations. Eq. (1) describes the temperature distribution in the liquid medium (liq), Eq. (2) describes the temperature distribution in the capsule material (cap) and Eq. (3) describes the temperature distribution of the PCM in a spherical shape.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_{liq} \rho_{liq} c_{p,liq} \frac{\partial T_{liq}}{\partial t} + \phi_{liq} u \rho_{liq} c_{p,liq} \frac{\partial T_{liq}}{\partial z} \\ = \lambda_{liq} \frac{\partial^2 T_{liq}}{\partial z^2} + q_{liq,cap} + \sum q_{source} - \sum q_{sink} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\phi_{cap} \rho_{cap} c_{p,cap} \frac{\partial T_{cap}}{\partial t} = \lambda_{cap} \frac{\partial^2 T_{cap}}{\partial z^2} + q_{cap,liq} + q_{cap,pcm} \quad (2)$$

$$\rho_{pcm} \frac{\partial h_{pcm}}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\lambda_{pcm} r^2 \frac{\partial T_{pcm}}{\partial r} \right) + q_{pcm,cap} \quad (3)$$

Here, $\phi(-)$ is the volume fraction, ρ (kg m^{-3}) the density, c_p ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) the specific heat capacity, T (K) the temperature, u (m s^{-1}) the speed of the liquid medium, z (m) the vertical coordinate (starting from the bottom of the storage), λ ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) the thermal conductivity or heat transfer coefficient (depending on context), h (J kg^{-1}) the specific enthalpy, and r (m) the radius of the PCM capsule, considered as spherical. Coupling terms link the energy equations together and source and sink terms add or remove thermal energy into or from the storage. The following assumptions were made:

- In Eqs. (1) and (2) radial temperature gradients are neglected.
- In Eqs. (1) and (2) there is no phase change.
- All flows are fully developed.
- Convection effects within the storage and in the PCM are neglected.

Fig. 1. Flowchart for system model optimization using NOMAD optimizer. The hybrid sensible-latent TES (SHTES) is shown with stratification and layers of PCM capsules. Other abbreviations: photovoltaics (PV), heat pump (HP), heat exchanger (HEX), electricity (BC EC), domestic hot water (BC DHW) and space heating (BC SH).

- Properties of water (capacity, density, conductivity) are independent of temperature.

The coupling terms, corresponding to the heat transfer rates between water (lqd), capsule (cap) and PCM (pcm) within. $q_{lqd,cap}$ and $q_{cap,lqd}$ couple the energy Eqs. (1) and (2) and $q_{cap,pcm}$ and $q_{pcm,cap}$ couple the energy Eqs. (2) and (3) and are described as follows:

$$q_{lqd,cap} = \frac{U_{lqd,cap} A_{cap} f_{cap}}{V} (T_{cap} - T_{lqd}) \quad (4)$$

$$q_{cap,lqd} = \frac{U_{lqd,cap} A_{cap} f_{cap}}{V} (T_{lqd} - T_{cap}) \quad (5)$$

$$q_{cap,pcm} = \frac{U_{pcm,cap} A_{cap} f_{cap}}{V} (T_{pcm} - T_{cap}) \quad (6)$$

$$q_{pcm,cap} = \frac{U_{pcm,cap} A_{cap} f_{cap}}{V} (T_{cap} - T_{pcm}) \quad (7)$$

where $U_{lqd,cap}$ ($W m^{-2} K^{-1}$) is the overall heat-transfer coefficient between the liquid and the outside of the capsule shell (external convection + shell conduction), $U_{pcm,cap}$ ($W m^{-2} K^{-1}$) is the overall heat-transfer coefficient between the PCM and the inside of the shell (pure conduction through the shell), A_{cap} (m^2) is the external surface area of a single capsule, f_{cap} (-) is the number of capsules in the current finite-volume layer, V (m^3) is the geometric volume of the corresponding finite-volume layer.

The source and sink terms can be described as follows in Eq. (8):

$$\sum q_{source} + \sum q_{sink} = \frac{U_{loss} A_{loss}}{V} (T_{lqd} - T_{sur}) + \sum_k \left(\frac{\dot{m}_k c_{p,lqd}}{V} (T_{lqd} - T_{k,noz}) \right) \quad (8)$$

where U_{loss} ($W m^{-2} K^{-1}$) is the heat loss coefficient, A_{loss} (m^2) the loss area, T_{sur} (K) the surrounding/ambient temperature, \dot{m}_k ($kg s^{-1}$)

the mass flow rate through nozzle k , $c_{p,lqd}$ ($J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$) the liquid heat capacity, and $T_{k,noz}$ (K) the inlet or outlet temperature at nozzle k .

This equation captures both heat losses to the surroundings and energy exchange via flow through the storage nozzles. The first term on the right-hand side, $U_{loss} A_{loss} (T_{lqd} - T_{sur})$, accounts for heat loss through the tank boundaries, where U_{loss} is the overall heat transfer coefficient, A_{loss} is the surface area for heat transfer, and $T_{lqd} - T_{sur}$ is the temperature difference driving this loss. For each storage concept, U_{loss} is determined by the sum of conduction through the chosen insulation layer (vacuum gap, PUR foam, or advanced basement insulation) and conduction through an additional layer of soil, modeled here as a fixed ($d_{Ground} = 1$ m) radial/axial thickness of ground around the tank with temperatures based on undisturbed ground temperature profiles using the method proposed by Marquez et al. [42]. Although thermal losses are continuous, the ground around the tank warms up over the first one or two cycles and then stabilizes. Detailed multi-layer simulations show that, after about two years, the start-of-year and end-of-year soil temperatures converge. To reduce the computational load for large-scale optimization, we therefore approximate the ground with a single soil layer and initialize each annual cycle at the previous year's final temperature, rather than modeling multiple concentric SoTTESS layers.

Eq. (9) shows the simplified 1D form for the overall heat transfer coefficient over the wall, where d_{ins} and λ_{ins} are the insulation thickness and thermal conductivity, respectively, and $d_{soil} = 1$ m with λ_{soil} is the ground layer thickness and conductivity.

$$U_{loss} = \frac{1}{\frac{d_{ins}}{\lambda_{ins}} + \frac{d_{soil}}{\lambda_{soil}}} \quad (9)$$

The second term represents the energy transfer from flow through various nozzles k , where \dot{m}_k is the mass flow rate through nozzle k , $c_{p,lqd}$ is the specific heat capacity of the liquid, V is the total volume of the storage system, and $T_{lqd} - T_{k,noz}$ represents the temperature

gradient between the storage liquid and the fluid flowing through nozzle k . This formulation allows for a dynamic representation of heat exchange, capturing both passive losses and active thermal energy transfer.

A nodal mixing model determines the effects of buoyancy-induced mixing. Increases in fluid density at lower temperatures cause cooler layers to sink and warmer layers to rise. The nodal mixing model assumes a point in time at which a warmer layer $i + 1$, located beneath a cooler layer i , completely mixes, and reaches a uniform temperature. This is expressed by Eq. (10):

$$T_{i+1}^{\text{new}} = T_i^{\text{new}} = \frac{m_i c_{p,i} T_i + m_{i+1} c_{p,i+1} T_{i+1}}{m_i c_{p,i} + m_{i+1} c_{p,i+1}} \quad (10)$$

Here, m_i (kg) is the mass in layer i , $c_{p,i}$ ($\text{J kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$) is the specific heat capacity of layer i , and T_i (K) is the temperature of layer i .

The finite volume method is used to discretize the equations. A uniform cell size is used for Eq. (10). Non-uniform cell sizes can be used for the energy Eqs. (1) and (2). This increases the positioning flexibility of the capsule layer in the storage and increases the simulation accuracy and speed, since the cell sizes at the corresponding positions for both energy equations are the same, but larger cells can be selected in non-overlapping, sensible areas. The central differentiation scheme is used for the spatial discretization of the diffusion terms. The convection term in Eq. (1) is discretized using the upwind/downwind scheme. The implicit backward differentiation scheme is used for temporal discretization. The thermophysical properties of the water and the capsule material are independent of temperature. The water values used correspond to a temperature of 35 °C.

However, the thermophysical properties of the PCM are different for the two different aggregate states, liquid and solid. During the phase change process, the specific heat capacity must be determined based on a defined melting range, as follows in Eq. (11):

$$c_{p,\text{pcm},\text{fus}} = \frac{\Delta h}{T_{\text{pcm},\text{f}} - T_{\text{pcm},\text{s}}} \quad (11)$$

where Δh (J kg^{-1}) is the enthalpy of fusion, and $T_{\text{pcm},\text{f}}$ and $T_{\text{pcm},\text{s}}$ are the upper and lower bounds of the melting range (K). An approximate skewed normal distribution approach [43] provides a continuous heat capacity function within the manufacturer-defined melting range.

The enthalpy of fusion, Δh , represents the amount of heat stored or released by the PCM as it transitions between solid and liquid phases. It is the energy required to fully melt the PCM from a solid to a liquid state without a temperature change, over a defined melting range. This melting range is represented by $T_{\text{pcm},\text{f}}$ and $T_{\text{pcm},\text{s}}$, which are the upper and lower bounds of the PCM's melting temperature, respectively. The specific heat capacity during phase transition, $c_{p,\text{pcm},\text{fus}}$, is derived by distributing the enthalpy of fusion across this melting range, allowing for a smooth temperature-dependent representation of the phase change.

The implemented energy Eq. (3) assumes a spherical capsule geometry. Thus, for any alternative capsule shape, the geometries are approximated using a hollow sphere of equal surface area and volume as spherical capsule equivalents [44]. The equivalent spherical capsule is generated with identical surface, thickness of the capsule material, and PCM quantity to the alternative shape. Due to the minimal surface area to volume ratio of a sphere, a cavity is assumed in the center of the sphere to compensate for the volume difference. Fig. 2 shows a simplified diagram of the logic and steps involved in the TES submodel.

The PV system's electricity generation is modeled based on Bellini et al. [45], as shown in Eq. (12):

$$I_P = I_{SC}(G_{GTI}, T) \left[1 - C_1 \left(e^{\frac{V_P}{e C_2 V_{OC}}} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (12)$$

where I_P (A) is the module current, I_{SC} (A) is the short-circuit current, V_P (V) is the module voltage, V_{OC} (V) is the open-circuit voltage, and C_1, C_2 are model-specific coefficients.

Fig. 2. Simplified flow diagram focusing on the TES submodel. A time-stepping loop (outer arrow) updates the solutions (Eqs. 1–3) each iteration. Coupling terms (Eqs. 4–7), boundary conditions (Eq. 8), buoyancy mixing (Eq. 11). Finally, the updated state is passed to the overarching system model.

Several adjustments were made to the Bellini model for improved accuracy. A correction term for irradiance dependence was omitted, and the temperature coefficients for voltage were modified to match data sheet specifications (typically given in %/°C). The adjusted equations for open-circuit voltage and maximum power point voltage are shown in Eqs. (13) and (14):

$$V_{OC} = V_{OCS} (1 + \beta \cdot (T - T_S)) \quad (13)$$

$$V_{MPP} = V_{MPPS} (1 + \beta \cdot (T - T_S)) \quad (14)$$

where V_{OCS} and V_{MPPS} are the reference open-circuit and maximum power point voltages, β is the temperature coefficient from the module data sheet, T is the current module temperature, and T_S is the reference temperature.

The module temperature T_{cell} is estimated using an empirical relation from Migan [46] as shown in Eq. (15):

$$T_{\text{cell}} = T_{\text{air}} + 0.035 \times G \quad (15)$$

where T_{air} is the ambient temperature and G is the irradiance. This adjustment addresses performance variations under peak sunlight by accounting for module heating effects, providing a more accurate reflection of real PV output.

The global oblique irradiation G_{GTI} on the PV module is determined as follows:

$$G_{GTI} = G_{BTI} + G_{DTI} + G_{RTI} \quad (16)$$

where G_{GTI} , G_{BTI} , G_{DTI} , G_{RTI} ($W m^{-2}$) represent the global, beam, diffuse, and reflected irradiances, respectively. They were determined using the Perez model [47]. The NOAA algorithm [48] was used to calculate the sun azimuth angle and the sun position angle. The model was additionally validated with PVSOL software [49].

The thermal energy delivered by the HP is determined using the following equations (Eq. 17 through 19):

$$\dot{Q}_{hp} = \dot{m}_{sink} c_{p,sink} (T_{sink,out} - T_{sink,in}) \quad (17)$$

$$P_{ele} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{hp}}{COP_{real}} \quad (18)$$

$$COP_{real} = \varphi \cdot COP_{Carnot} = \varphi \cdot \frac{T_{sink,out}}{T_{sink,out} - T_{sour,in}} \quad (19)$$

Here, \dot{Q}_{hp} (W) is the thermal power of the HP, \dot{m}_{sink} ($kg s^{-1}$) the mass flow rate on the sink side, $c_{p,sink}$ ($J kg^{-1} K^{-1}$) the specific heat capacity of the sink fluid, $T_{sink,out}$, $T_{sink,in}$, $T_{sour,in}$ (K) the relevant inlet/outlet temperatures, P_{ele} (W) the HP's electrical power consumption, COP_{Carnot} (-) the ideal (Carnot) COP, and φ (-) the HP quality factor (fraction of the ideal COP). To account for the dependency of the HP's quality grade, a linear regression as a function of the temperature difference across the HP was determined using operating points found in the literature for HPs available on the market. [50]

The overall system model operates with two time loops: an inner loop for quick-response dynamics of the thermal storage units with a time step of 10 s and an outer loop for PV and HP models, setting boundary conditions for the next cycle with a time step of 60 s. Fig. 3 shows a simplified diagram of the overall system model.

To ensure efficient operation of the heat pump (HP) in meeting both domestic hot water (DHW) and seasonal thermal energy storage (SHTES) requirements, the control strategy dynamically adapts based on real-time temperature conditions. In particular, the system first distinguishes between day and night using the flag `arg_flag_day`. During night-time operation, if the SHTES outlet temperature drops below 35,°C, the system enables grid usage by setting `hp_flag_Grid` to true. Conversely, during daytime operation, if the DHW temperature is below 59,°C, the system prioritizes DHW charging by setting `dhw_flag_charge` to true. The `Electrical_Distributor` then computes the available power for the HP, if at least 25 % of the rated HP power is available, the HP is activated to either charge DHW (up to 65,°C) or, if DHW is sufficiently warm, to charge the SHTES (up to 50,°C). When the HP is off, the building's heating is supplied directly from the SHTES, which delivers water from its top (maintained between 35 and 40,°C) while receiving return flows at 25–30,°C. Fig. 4 shows the control logic as a process diagram.

2.2.1. Component experimental validation

The photovoltaic (PV) model was validated by comparing its simulated annual yield to a reference scenario generated by PVSOL [49], a commercially validated software tool used for designing and optimizing PV systems. The reference scenario selected for comparison used Basel-Binningen weather data (Meteonorm climate data 1991–2010) and a JAP72S03-340/SC (JA Solar Holdings Co., Ltd) PV module with a tilt angle of 30° and a southern orientation (180° azimuth). An overall system efficiency of 96 % was assumed for both the reference and the in-house model. Over a one-year horizon beginning January 1st, the in-house PV model's output was summed monthly and annually, then compared with the PV*SOL reference results.

To validate the space heating and domestic hot water (DHW) demand profiles, an energy-balance approach was used. First, hourly heating

Fig. 3. Overview of the full system model's main time loop. At each iteration, weather and boundary conditions are updated, the PV model is evaluated, the heat pump and control logic decide on mass flows and power usage, the TES solver (see separate Fig. 2) is called, and finally sensor measurements and post-processing occur. The simulation continues until either time \geq timeMax or the steady-state criterion is met.

demand profiles were generated via the “Heating Degree Hour” methodology for given flow temperatures at various locations. These profiles were summed annually and compared against known or calculated annual heating demands (using area-specific heating demand and the heated area). In parallel, a plausibility check ensured the simulation's space-heating profile followed the derived load curves. If significant deviations arose, the temperature setpoints or system boundary conditions would be rechecked. This process confirmed whether the simulation reliably produced the expected heating consumption pattern (both in magnitude and in hourly/monthly distribution).

A test bench built at HSLU served to validate the hybrid TES model. The system comprises a heat pump (HP) to charge the buffer tank, a 300 L buffer tank filled with ellipsoidal capsules, and a floor heating mixing system was used for discharge as shown in Fig. 5. The TES unit is filled with $N = 2518$ ellipsoidal capsules filled with CrodaTherm32 (properties used are shown in Table 1) as PCM. Each capsule is an HDPE

Fig. 4. Flowchart of the heat pump control logic. The diagram outlines the decision process based on day/night conditions and temperature thresholds: during the night, if the SHTES top outlet falls below 35 °C, grid power is enabled (sh_flag_Grid); during the day, if the HWTES bottom temperature is below 59 °C, DHW charging is prioritized (dhw_flag_charge). The Electrical Distributor allocates the available PV power to the HP, which then either charges the HWTES (up to 65 °C) or the SHTES (up to 50 °C). In the absence of sufficient power, the HP remains off, and the building draws heat from the SHTES and HWTES respectively.

(properties used are shown in Table 6) shell with outer semi-axes (x,y,z) measuring 26.2, 52.4 and 104.8 mm and a uniform wall thickness of 1.5 mm and encloses an outer volume of $V_{cap} = 7.53 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^3$. Packing the capsules randomly inside the tank results in an effective packing density of 63.2 % (≈ 60 % if the tank volume above the filling port is included).

The test stand, shown schematically in Fig. 6, was instrumented with a series of sensors (temperature, mass flow, electrical power) detailed in Table 2. During tests, the tank was charged from about 21 °C to 40 °C and discharged from 40 °C back to 20 °C. Mass flows, inlet/outlet temperatures, and HP electrical power were recorded at high temporal resolution. The same boundary conditions (flow rates, ambient conditions, set point temperatures) were applied in simulation. Comparing measured vs. simulated charging/discharging powers and stored energy provided a direct measure of the model’s accuracy.

The in-house heat pump (HP) model was validated against measurement data from the same prototype test bench. Key operating data,

Fig. 5. Scheme of the test bench/prototype for PCM storage validation. (1) Heat pump circuit, (2) Buffer tank with PCM capsules, (3) Floor heating mixing group.

Table 1

Key properties of CrodaTherm32 used as PCM in the validation experiments.

Property	CrodaTherm32
Melting T [°C]	32
Enthalpy [kJ/kg]	176.4
$c_{p,liq}$ [kJ/kg·K]	1.4
$c_{p,sol}$ [kJ/kg·K]	2.3
ρ_{liq} [kg/L]	0.88
ρ_{sol} [kg/L]	0.88
λ [W/m·K]	0.19

such as water-side inlet and outlet temperatures at the condenser and evaporator, electrical power draw of the HP, and water mass flows, were recorded. The measured thermal output of the HP was calculated and compared to the HP model’s simulated results over identical charging/discharging cycles.

2.3. Boundary conditions and scenarios

The reference building used in this study is a typical Swiss multi-family dwelling located in Bern [4]. The building consists of eight apartments distributed over four floors, with a total living space of 800 m² and a roof area of 264 m², which is used for photovoltaic installations. The occupancy is assumed to be 20 residents, which influences the aggregated space heating and domestic hot water (DHW) demand.

While the specific location is Bern, the conditions modeled are representative of many regions in Europe that experience similar temperate climates with cold winters and moderate summers. Therefore, the findings from this study can be applied broadly to regions with comparable weather patterns and architectural contexts, particularly in areas where multi-family residential buildings are common.

The building’s space heating requirements are based on climatic data from Meteonorm [51], calculated using Heating Degree Day and Hour methods, considering a yearly space heating requirement of 30 W/m² K and a total heating area of 924 m² with a minimal supply temperature of 35 °C and a fixed return temperature of 25 °C. DHW demand follows SIA 385/1:2020 standards [52], and realistic usage profiles from DHWCalc [53] were used, assuming the inlet fresh tap water comes at a constant 10 °C. Electrical demand is based on HTW Berlin’s dataset [54], adapted to Swiss residential consumption trends [55].

Building on these demands, we explore three different thermal storage concepts, each featuring distinct insulation strategies and design constraints:

Vacuum Insulated Tank (VIT): A double-walled, cylindrical tank with an evacuated annular space, providing extremely low thermal conductivity and mitigating moisture ingress. However, the specialized manufacturing results in higher costs and embodied emissions.

Fig. 6. Schematic of validation setup with sensor placement.

Spherical Storage Tank (SST): A glass-fiber-reinforced plastic (GFRP) sphere from Planergie AG (operating as energy4me) [56] with a 0.3 m polyurethane (PUR) foam layer. Although simpler to produce than a vacuum-insulated design, the practical volume is limited by transportation constraints (diameter up to ~ 4 m).

Repurposed Basement Storage (RBS): A cuboidal, water-tight conversion of unused basement space. Advanced waterproof insulation (0.2–0.3 m), developed in joint project with HSLU and SFOE including SwissporXPS [57] is applied to existing walls, effectively reducing capital costs by leveraging the existing structure.

Table 3 summarizes the thickness and thermal conductivity (λ) of each concept’s insulation, as well as the surrounding ground layer and the domestic hot water tank. These values form the basis for calculating the overall heat-transfer coefficient in Section 2.2.

2.4. Optimization framework

The system employs the NOMAD (Nonlinear Optimization by Mesh Adaptive Direct search) optimizer (version 4.3.1) for configuring its settings, particularly focusing on enhancing thermal self-sufficiency, minimizing the Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH), and reducing the Global Warming Potential (GWP). NOMAD is well-suited for complex,

resource-intensive simulations involving non-smooth or discontinuous functions without derivatives [41].

Thermal self-sufficiency is defined as the ratio of the total heat supplied by the HP, powered by the system’s photovoltaic (PV) generation, to the building’s total heat consumption over the year. This metric excludes any excess electricity generated by PV that is fed back into the grid, focusing solely on the heat generated by the system’s own renewable sources relative to total heat demand.

$$SS_{th} = \frac{E_{PVth}}{E_{Sth} + E_{DHWth}} \quad (20)$$

LCOH is a key performance indicator used to calculate the average cost of producing a unit of energy over the system’s lifetime, including construction, operation, maintenance, and electricity from the grid [8]:

$$LCOH = \frac{CAPEX \cdot ANF + OPEX}{E_{HP,direct} + E_{TES}} \quad (21)$$

Where CAPEX stands for capital investment costs, OPEX for operating expenses, and ANF is the annuity factor calculated using the formula:

$$ANF_{t,i} = \frac{i(1+i)^t}{(1+i)^t - 1} \quad (22)$$

Where i is the interest rate and t is the lifespan of the system, assumed to be 20 years, and the Operational expenses (OPEX) account for electricity costs required to operate the HP, as well as maintenance costs, which are estimated at 3.5 % of the initial investment annually. This percentage reflects standard industry practice for covering ongoing system upkeep and minor repairs.

Table 2
Overview of sensors in the test bench (short descriptions).

Sensor	Measurement	Circuit
T01	Return temp.	Floor heating
T02	Flow temp.	Floor heating
T03	Return (pre-mix)	Floor heating
T04	Flow (post-mix)	Floor heating
T05	Buffer → floor flow	Buffer
T06	Floor → buffer return	Buffer
T07	HP → buffer flow	Buffer
T08	Buffer → HP return	Buffer
T09–T12	Cond./Evap. inlet/outlet	Heat pump
T13–T16	Temps. at buffer levels	Buffer
Coriolis	Flow (floor heating)	Floor heating
Vol. flow (MIC)	Buffer → floor flow	Buffer
Vortex flow (1)	HP → buffer flow	Buffer
Vortex flow (2)	HP heat source	Heat pump
$P_{el,HP}$	Electrical HP power	Heat pump
Conductivity	Water quality/salt leak	Buffer

Table 3
Thickness and thermal conductivity of ground and insulation layers.

Component	Thickness [m]	λ [W/(m·K)]
Ground (surrounding)	1.00	1.80
RBS (insulation)	0.24	0.0363
VIT (insulation)	0.30	0.0040
SST (insulation)	0.25	0.0250
DHW tank (insulation)	0.15	0.0350

GHGE assessments use the Global Warming Potential (GWP) metric, expressed in kilograms of CO₂-equivalent (CO₂-eq). This metric compares the environmental impacts of different technologies and is crucial for the project's sustainability efforts. By integrating GWP into the economic model, carbon pricing (120 CHF per ton of CO₂) allows the GWP to be compared directly with LCOH in CHF per kWh [58,59].

Weighting in multi-objective optimization allows for the expression of preferences among competing objectives, tailored to specific needs. The NOMAD optimizer employs a weighted sum method, consolidating multiple objectives into a single function by summing each objective function f_i multiplied by its respective weighting coefficient w_i (Eq. 23). Each weighting factor includes a normalization component θ_i multiplied by the assigned arbitrary weight p_i to ensure equitable consideration among objectives, as shown in Eqs. (24) and (25) [60].

$$\min_{x \in \Omega} F(x) = \sum_{i=1}^j w_i \cdot f_i(x) \quad (23)$$

$$w_i \geq 0, \forall i = 1, \dots, j \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{i=1}^j w_i = 1 \quad (24)$$

$$w_i = p_i \cdot \theta_i \quad (25)$$

Optimization primarily targets achieving thermal self-sufficiency (SS_{th}) between 70 % and 100 %. Weighting factors for LCOH and GWP are denoted as p_{LCOH} and p_{GWP} , respectively, with the remaining weighting evenly split between these objectives (Eqs. (26) and (27)).

$$p_{LCOH} = \frac{1 - p_{SS}}{2} \quad (26)$$

$$p_{GWP} = \frac{1 - p_{SS}}{2} \quad (27)$$

Normalization, as per Grodzevich et al. [60], adjusts factors based on Utopia and Nadir points to define optimization boundaries. The Utopia point represents the best theoretical value, and the Nadir point the least favorable, calculated using Eqs. (28) and (29).

$$z_i^U = \min_x f_i(x) : x \in \Omega \quad (28)$$

$$z_i^N = \max_x f_i(x) : x \in \Omega \quad (29)$$

The complete optimization function integrates the KPIs, weighting factors, and normalization into a single objective function. This function, denoted as $F(x)$, represents the objective to be minimized during the optimization process. The function is expressed as shown in Eq. (30).

$$\min_{x \in \Omega} F(x) = \frac{1 - p_{SS}}{2} \cdot \theta_{LCOH} \cdot f_{LCOH} + \frac{1 - p_{SS}}{2} \cdot \theta_{GWP} \cdot f_{GWP} + p_{SS} \cdot (1 - f_{SS}) \quad (30)$$

This function encapsulates the multi-objective nature of the problem, facilitating the search for the optimal solution by balancing LCOH, GWP, and self-sufficiency. Fig. 7 shows a simplified breakdown of the overall optimization process.

Key variables adjusted during optimization include storage unit sizes SHTES and HWTES, PCM capsule shape, size, and phase change temperature, PV peak power and orientation, and maximum HP power. These variables significantly impact system performance and costs, and the ranges considered here are shown in Table 4.

For the photovoltaic (PV) system, optimization variables include the number of panels and their orientation in azimuth (horizontal angle, ϕ) and tilt (vertical angle, α). Increasing the panel count enhances energy self-sufficiency by capturing more solar energy, but also raises costs and GWP proportionally.

Fig. 7. Flow diagram of the optimization procedure. The outer optimization iterations scan w_{SS} from 0 to 1 (in steps of e.g. 0.1). For each fixed w_{SS} , the inner loop (NOMAD) iteratively refines the design variables. At convergence, the dataset for that w_{SS} is stored, and w_{SS} is incremented. Finally, all solutions are collated and analyzed to produce the Pareto front.

Orientation is critical for maximizing solar capture, with ideal angles varying by location, climate, and the sun's path. The project building, specified to have a flat roof, has a total roof area of 264 m². However, only 66 % of this area is viable for PV installations due to structural and shading constraints, as indicated by Anderegg et al. [61]. This limitation affects the maximum number of panels that can be effectively utilized, influencing the design and range of the PV system setup.

Table 4
Overview of the ranges for the optimization variables.

Properties	Lower bound	Upper bound
SHTES tank height [m]	1	3
SHTES tank width [m]	1	4
PCM Section rel. height [-]	0.1	0.9
PCM Capsule Size [ml]	135	5000
PCM Capsule Type [-]	CAP-1	CAP-4
PCM Type [-]	PCM-1	PCM-4
PCM T_{pc} [°C]	40	48
DHW tank height [m]	2	2.5
DHW tank width [m]	0.5	1.8
Amount of PV panels [-]	0	95
PV Azimuth angle [°]	90	270
PV Tilt angle [°]	0	45
Electrical power HP [kW]	4	40

The study utilizes Suntech 380 W mono-crystalline solar modules, known for their high efficiency (20.8 %) and reliability. Each panel has a maximum power output of 0.380 kWp, with dimensions of 1,756 mm in height, 1,039 mm in width, and 35 mm in thickness, weighing 20.3 kg.

These state-of-the-art modules ensure consistent performance across various configurations [62].

The electrical power of the air source HP is a key variable in the optimization model, affecting system performance, cost, GWP, and the ability to efficiently charge the SHTES. The HP power range is set between 4 kW and 40 kW electric, covering typical capacities for commercial air source HPs, allowing modulation between 25 % and 100 % of the maximum power to meet varying demands.

The packed bed section of the SHTES is defined by the height ratio or packed bed thickness, ranging from 10–90 % to maintain a 10 % sensible buffer zone at the bottom of the storage tank. Capsule shapes, crucial for optimizing this type of thermal storage, include spheres, cylinders (aspect ratio 2.5), ellipsoids (aspect ratio 2.5), and a superellipsoid (COWA Booster Capsules) from the company COWA Thermal Solutions AG (COWA). These shapes were selected based on their surface-to-volume ratios and packing density. The surface-to-volume ratios are calculated using the super ellipsoid model and a polynomial regression was applied to the results to estimate the surface for capsules ranging from 100 ml to 5 l, ensuring precise model adjustments for enhanced thermal performance.

(a) Capsule Surface Area vs Volume.

(b) 3D plots of different shapes

(c) Render of example packed bed section for each concept.

(d) Packing Density by Capsule Type and Container Shape

Fig. 8. Overview of different shapes and properties. (a) Surface Area vs Volume, (b) 3D shape plots, (c) 3D render of PB sections, (d) Packing Density comparison.

Table 5
Key properties of PCM candidates from COWA TS.

Property	PCM-1	PCM-2	PCM-3	PCM-4
Melting T [°C]	40	42	45	48
Enthalpy [kJ/kg]	241	178	208	210
$c_{p,liq}$ [kJ/kg·K]	3.1	3.1	3.1	3.1
$c_{p,sol}$ [kJ/kg·K]	2.9	2.9	2.9	2.9
ρ_{liq} [kg/L]	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3
ρ_{sol} [kg/L]	1.3	1.3	1.3	1.3

To estimate packing density, rigid body simulations were performed, modeling the spatial arrangement of 135 mL capsules within 1 m³ containers under ideal packing conditions. This approach provides a conservative estimate while accounting for boundary effects, which diminish with larger containers and more capsules (see [63]).

Fig. 8 provides a detailed comparison of capsule shapes and their packing efficiencies, which are critical for optimizing the storage design. In subfigure (a), the relationship between surface area and volume for different capsule shapes, spheres, ellipsoids, cylinders, and COWA Boosters, is illustrated, with regression lines showing how surface area scales with volume, which is essential for heat transfer. Subfigure (b) visually presents 3D models of each capsule shape, highlighting their design characteristics: spheres for minimal surface area, ellipsoids and cylinders for intermediate surface area, and COWA Boosters for maximized thermal contact. Subfigure (c) shows packed bed renders for each storage concept (SST, VIT, and RBS), demonstrating how capsule shapes fit within different tank geometries. Finally, subfigure (d) compares the packing densities achieved by each shape in various containers, with COWA Boosters achieving the highest density, optimizing space and thermal capacity. This figure collectively emphasizes how capsule geometry and container design impact storage efficiency and thermal performance.

This study incorporates four phase change materials (PCMs) developed by COWA TS, including PCM-4, which has already reached the market. All four materials are sodium acetate trihydrate (SAT)-based and rely on undisclosed additives to tune properties such as phase-change enthalpy and melting temperature. Table 5 summarizes their key thermophysical properties.

SAT, and SAT-based PCM can exhibit sub-cooling, where the material cools below its nominal melting temperature before solidification begins, potentially affecting heat release rates and overall reliability. In practice, sub-cooling is often mitigated by additives, nucleation agents, or specific operating protocols. Because this research aims at system-level techno-economic and environmental optimization, we assume this effect is negligible under normal operating conditions considering the enhanced formulations from COWA TS. Consequently, while we have accurate inputs for modeling, details about the chemical composition or specific additive mechanisms remain outside this study's scope. Instead, we focus on the essential parameters (melting range, latent heat, density) that directly influence thermal performance, cost, and GWP, thereby ensuring that the techno-economic and environmental evaluations accurately capture the PCM's overall behavior despite the confidential additive formulations.

Because the additives' mass fractions are similar across these variations, our global GWP and LCOH calculations are standardized to reflect comparable environmental impacts and costs. Since the additives themselves are proprietary, only aggregated performance data (e.g., thermal conductivity, heat capacity, enthalpy) were shared with the research team.

Table 6 shows the additional thermophysical properties used in the simulations for both the reference heat-transfer fluid (water at 30 °C) and the outer 1.5 mm thick HDPE capsule shell.

These material constants are applied uniformly to every capsule shape considered in the optimisation; only the geometric parameters

Table 6
Thermo-physical properties of the heat-transfer fluid (liquid water, $T = 30$ °C, 1 bar) from CoolProp and HDPE for capsule shell.

Property	Water (30 °C)	HDPE (Cap. Shell)
ρ [kg/m ³]	995.65	963
c_p [kJ/kg·K]	4.18	1.90
λ [W/m·K]	0.614	0.350
μ [Pa·s]	7.97×10^{-4}	–
ν [m ² /s]	8.01×10^{-7}	–

Table 7
PCM additional material and production costs.

PCM Costs	Cost (CHF)
PCM Costs (C_{PCM})	1 CHF/kg
Mixing Costs (C_{MIX})	135.63 CHF/m ³
Capsule Material (C_{CapMat})	2.1 CHF/kg
Capsule production ($C_{CapProd}$)	0.0554 CHF/capsule
Capsule filling ($C_{CapFill}$)	0.2 CHF/capsule

(volume, surface area and packing density) vary with the design variables in Table 4.

2.4.1. Cost functions

The cost functions used for the optimization of the hybrid system components are summarized in Table 12 in Appendix A. These functions are derived from various sources to reflect realistic investment and operational costs. The PV system costs are modeled as piecewise linear functions based on the installed peak power (PV_{kWp}) and incorporate price increases due to recent market fluctuations [64,65]. The cost function for the heat pump (HP) was developed by integrating catalogue data from Stiebel Eltron [66] and CTA AG [67], along with methodological guidance from the IGE comparison calculator [68]. This function incorporates costs for additional components beyond the heat pump itself, including valves, air ducting, installation, electrical setup, connection, and the control cabinet. By superimposing these individual cost functions, a comprehensive model was established to represent the total investment. This final model was validated against other industry data, including Berger et al. [24], the CKW heating calculator [69], and the SensOpt annual report [40]. For PCM capsules, the cost function accounts for material, mixing, encapsulation, and production costs, which were provided by COWA and are consistent with independent estimates [70]. Thermal energy storage (TES) costs vary by configuration: vacuum insulated tanks (VIT), repurposed basement storage (RBS), and spherical storage tanks (SST) all have specific cost functions based on volume, surface area, and insulation thickness [20,57]. Additionally, excavation costs for TES systems are considered as a function of total storage volume [20]. For further details on PCM material and production costs, Table 7 outlines the individual cost components.

The cost information for the PCM and capsule production shown in Table 7 was provided by COWA TS AG. The PCM cost order of magnitude is also confirmed by Carnie et al. [70]. The capsule production and filling costs are considered constant as they are bound to the process and thus to the number of capsules instead of capsule shape or volume.

2.4.2. GWP functions

The global warming potential (GWP) of each system component is evaluated using lifecycle assessments (LCA), covering production, operational, and disposal phases. Table 13 in Appendix A summarizes the GWP functions for the key components. For the PV system, the GWP is based on the manufacturing footprint of Mono-Si modules, with a fixed value per installed kWp [58,59,71,72]. The GWP of HPs is modeled with a quadratic function that scales with thermal capacity, with the majority of emissions resulting from electricity consumption during

operation [16–18,39,73]. TES systems have distinct GWP functions depending on the configuration: vacuum insulated tanks (VIT), repurposed basement storage (RBS), and spherical storage tanks (SST) each consider the materials and insulation used, with data from environmental product declarations (EPDs) [56,74–76]. The GWP for PCM capsules is estimated based on an internal LCA from COWA, which includes the environmental impact of the production process and material inputs [70]. Finally, the GWP contribution from grid electricity usage is calculated based on the Swiss grid mix average of 0.128 kg CO₂-eq/kWh [72]. The total GWP is converted into financial terms using Switzerland's carbon pricing scheme, which applies a rate of 120 CHF per ton of CO₂ [13].

2.4.3. Base case

For reference, the system presented in this study is compared to fuel oil boilers. The LCOH of an oil boiler is 0.14 CHF/kWh, assuming a 20-year operational lifetime [14]. The GWP of an oil boiler, adjusted for operational efficiency, is calculated at 0.03831 CHF per kWh, considering the Swiss carbon price of 120 CHF/ton of CO₂-eq [13]. In the comparison of heating systems across urban, suburban, and rural areas, the oil boiler demonstrates a consistent LCOH of 0.14 CHF/kWh, highlighting its cost stability irrespective of location. This makes the oil boiler a comparatively uniform and potentially cost-effective option across diverse geographical contexts, unlike other technologies that exhibit greater cost variability.

2.5. Statistical analysis

In addition to the techno-economic and environmental optimization, statistical methods were employed to evaluate the influence of each input parameter (e.g., PV peak power, HP peak power, SHTES volume) on the key performance indicators (KPIs), namely, thermal self-sufficiency (SS_{th}), Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH), and Global Warming Potential (GWP).

First, we used Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to assess the statistical significance of each parameter with respect to the KPIs. This method partitions the total variability observed in the KPIs into contributions attributable to each parameter, thereby determining which design variables exert the strongest impact on system performance.

In a second step we performed a Spearman correlation analysis [77] to complement ANOVA by quantifying the strength and direction of monotonic relationships among parameters themselves and between parameters and KPIs. Spearman's rank-based approach does not assume linearity or normally distributed data, making it particularly suitable for complex building- and storage-related simulations, which often exhibit nonlinear interactions. Previous building energy studies have likewise applied correlation analysis to pinpoint drivers of consumption and performance gaps [78,79]. In our case, Spearman correlation highlights how increases or decreases in a given parameter (e.g., tank volume) tend to coincide with changes in a KPI, while also revealing any interdependencies between parameters.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Validation results

3.1.1. PV model validation

Fig. 9 illustrates a validation test for the photovoltaic (PV) model, comparing the simulated instantaneous electrical energy (blue) against data produced using PV*SOL for the exact same system (orange). The left plot shows the hourly energy generation, and the right plot depicts the cumulative energy over the same period of time.

Quantitatively, the model achieves a mean absolute error (MAE) of about 0.24 kWh and a root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.46 kWh for the instantaneous electrical energy, with an R^2 of 0.85. For the cumulative energy, the MAE is approximately 20.9 kWh, and the final energy error is around 65.4 kWh, corresponding to a final energy mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of about 1.0 %. These results confirm that the PV model accurately captures both short-term variability and

Fig. 9. Validation of the PV model using PV*SOL. Shown are hourly yields from the in-house model (blue) vs. PV*SOL (orange) on the left, and cumulative yearly yields on the right.

overall energy production, making it suitable for annual performance evaluations.

3.1.2. Hybrid TES model validation

Fig. 10 illustrates a typical charging test for the hybrid TES, where the temperatures and the integrated stored energy are shown for measured (solid) and simulated (dashed) data. In our charging validation, two separate experiments were conducted under slightly different conditions. In the first charging case, the temperature sensors T13–T16 exhibited mean absolute errors (MAE) ranging from about 0.39 °C–1.13 °C with R^2 values above 0.95, while in the second case the MAE increased slightly (up to 1.53 °C at T16) but still maintained high R^2 (approximately 0.94–0.99). Although the instantaneous power predictions show relatively higher percentage errors (MAPE around 31 %–35 %), these discrepancies are primarily attributed to uncertainty in the initial state of the PCM, a tight melting temperature window, the averaging of the phase change temperature and enthalpy over cooling and heating cycles, as well as introduced sensor noise from the validation inputs into the simulation. Importantly, the integrated energy error remains below 3 % in charging, with the total energy transferred from simulation deviating by less than 2 %–3 % from the experimental values.

Fig. 11 shows a typical discharging phase where the storage cools from about 40 °C to 20 °C. Two discharging experiments were analyzed. In the first discharging case, the MAE for temperature sensors T13–T16 ranged from about 0.55 °C to 1.49 °C, with coefficients of determination (R^2) between 0.984 and 0.997. The final energy error remained below 8 %. In the second discharging case, the temperature errors were somewhat higher (MAE up to about 1.46 °C), yet the model still maintained acceptable performance ($R^2 > 0.95$), and the integrated energy discrepancy remained within approximately 9 %.

Although instantaneous power predictions during discharging show larger uncertainty (MAPE values of about 29 %–37 %), the causes mirror those identified for the charging tests. Even so, the relatively high R^2 values for temperature and the low percentage errors in cumulative energy

Fig. 10. Left: Temperatures T13–T16 (positions in Table 2) over a charging cycle. Right: Charging power and the integrated energy stored in the buffer tank. Dashed lines: simulation; solid lines: experiment.

Fig. 12. Left: Comparison of Heat pump power vs simulation. Right: Cumulative thermal energy provided over time.

Fig. 11. Left: Temperatures T13–T16 (positions in Table 2) over a discharging cycle. Right: Discharging power and the integrated energy stored in the buffer tank.

transfer confirm the model’s robustness under varied operating conditions. These validation results provide confidence in using the model for subsequent annual performance simulations.

3.1.3. Heat pump model validation

Fig. 12 shows a representative validation test for the heat pump (HP) model, comparing the simulated thermal power output on the

sink side (blue) with the measured experimental data (orange). The left panel presents the instantaneous power, while the right panel shows the cumulative thermal energy delivered over time.

Quantitatively, the model captures the HP’s behavior with a mean absolute error (MAE) of about 0.36 kW and a RMSE of 0.46 kW, yielding a mean absolute percentage error (MAPE) of roughly 5.6 % for the instantaneous power. The coefficient of determination (R^2) for the power output is 0.795, indicating a reasonably good fit given measurement uncertainties and transient effects. In terms of integrated energy, the final energy error remains under 1.5 %, confirming that the model reliably predicts total heat output over a full charge cycle. These results are deemed sufficiently accurate for annual simulations, where short-term fluctuations in power have less impact on the overall performance assessment.

3.2. Overview and discussion of model outputs

The results presented in this section are illustrative examples that demonstrate the model’s capabilities. These examples set the stage for the later optimization, where the model is fully applied to explore different system configurations and performance trade-offs. The performance for both the seasonal sensible-only TES (SSTES) and the seasonal hybrid TES (SHTES) systems is summarized in Table 8. Both systems use a 9.24 m³ RBS type tank and a 1.85 m³ HWTES, with identical PV and HP capacities. However, the SHTES incorporates 2655 PCM capsules, occupying 52 % of the total SHTES volume (90 % of the storage height) and increasing its overall storage capacity by approximately 70 %. In order to monitor the temperature distribution within the tank, five thermocouples (T1–T5) were strategically placed at different heights on the water side, as illustrated in Fig. 13.

In the SSTES, the temperature distribution throughout the year, presented in Fig. 14, shows substantial stratification and fluctuation. The top layer (T5) consistently remains close to 50 °C, while the bottom layer (T1) frequently drops below 30 °C, especially during winter months. These fluctuations indicate that the SSTES struggles to maintain a uniform temperature profile, particularly during colder months when solar

Table 8
Summary of inputs for example RBS system.

Property	SSTES Sensible	SHTES Hybrid
Self-Sufficiency Thermal [%]	79.9	84.6
LCOH [CHF/kWh]	0.325	0.334
GWP [CHF/kWh]	9.95 E-03	1.18 E-02
Self-Sufficiency Electric [%]	39.9	40.4
PV Self-Consumption [%]	42.5	44.2
Comfort level [%]	99.1	99.1
PV Power [kWp]	36.1	36.1
PV Azimuth [deg]	180	180
PV Tilt [deg]	45	45
HP power [kWe]	23	23
STES Tank Volume [m ³]	9.24	9.24
STES Tank Height [m]	3	3
STES Tank Diameter [m]	1.76	1.76
Total number of capsules [-]	-	2655
Capsule volume [L]	-	2
Capsule type [-]	-	CAP-4
PCM Type [-]	-	PCM-1
PCM T_m [°C]	-	40
Total PCM mass [kg]	-	6335
Total PCM volume [m ³]	-	4.9
Total Capsule mass [kg]	-	402
HWTES Volume [m ³]	1.85	1.85
HWTES Height [m]	1.5	1.5
HWTES Diameter [m]	1.25	1.25

Fig. 13. Schematic of the thermal energy storage tank showing thermocouple locations (T1 to T5). The diagram also illustrates the packed bed section and thermal stratification zones.

availability is lower. Additionally, as presented in Fig. 15 energy availability in the SSTES ranges from 300 kWh in winter to 500 kWh in summer, showing considerable variation throughout the year. This fluctuation suggests that the system is heavily dependent on external energy input during colder periods and operates near full charge from May to October.

In comparison, the SHTES displays more stable temperature profiles across the measurement points, as shown in Fig. 14. The PCM section of the storage stabilizes around its phase change temperature of 40 °C, significantly dampening the temperature swings observed in the SSTES. This stability is quantitatively reflected in the lower standard deviations observed in the SHTES, particularly at sensors T2 and T5, where values are 9.88 K and 4.93 K in the SHTES compared to 10.75 K and 5.27 K in the SSTES. Additionally, the RMSE between the systems ranges from 2.73 K to 4.99 K, indicating that the SHTES maintains more consistent temperature levels across different sensor positions. This more stable temperature profile contributes to a reduced temperature gradient in the SHTES, with an average of -7.75 K compared to -9.37 K in the SSTES. The PCM capsules play a crucial role in this stability by dynamically interacting with the surrounding water, thereby smoothing fluctuations and supporting a more uniform temperature distribution, even during high-demand periods, such as winter. However, this stability does not necessarily translate into better long-term stratification, as both systems show minimal stratification persistence.

As presented in Fig. 15, the energy availability in the SHTES is also notably higher, ranging from 500 kWh during winter to 800 kWh in

Fig. 14. Yearly temperature distribution in sensible (top) and hybrid (bottom) STES for example RBS system using daily averaged data.

summer. This improvement can be attributed to the PCM capsules, which add approximately 320 kWh of thermal energy throughout the year, providing critical backup during periods of low solar availability.

Fig. 16 shows the Sankey diagram of energy flows in the hybrid system. The SHTES supplies 60 %–70 % of domestic hot water (DHW) demand, significantly reducing the heat pump load. Approximately 30 %–40 % of the PV-generated electricity is used directly for household needs, with excess energy either powering the heat pump or being fed into the grid. Grid electricity covers any remaining demand, with the overall system design maximizing self-sufficiency and making effective use of renewable energy.

Fig. 17 presents a normalized comparison of Sensible and SHTES systems, including the Sensible RBS, Hybrid RBS, Hybrid VIT, and Hybrid SST, relative to a conventional oil boiler, evaluated across five key performance indicators: thermal self-sufficiency, leveled cost of heat (LCOH), global warming potential (GWP), electrical self-sufficiency, and PV self-consumption. The three hybrid systems, RBS, VIT, and SST, all demonstrate high thermal self-sufficiency, ranging from 84.60 % to 84.80 %, with the Sensible RBS system slightly lower at 79.90 %. The oil boiler, as expected, exhibits no thermal self-sufficiency (0 %). The oil boiler has the lowest LCOH (0.140 CHF/kWh), but its environmental impact is the highest, with a GWP of 0.038 CHF/kWh, compared to the significantly lower values of 0.010–0.014 CHF/kWh for the other systems. Electrical self-sufficiency is similar across all SHTES systems, with values ranging from 39.90 % to 40.50 %, while the oil boiler provides no contribution. PV self-consumption is slightly higher for the Hybrid VIT and SST systems (44.30 % and 44.00 %, respectively) compared to the Sensible and Hybrid RBS systems (42.50 % and 44.20 %).

Across all systems, the PV system and heat pump dominate the investment costs, contributing around 80–90 %. The Sensible RBS system has the lowest total CAPEX (200,000 CHF), while the Hybrid systems, especially Hybrid VIT, see a slight increase (up to 235,000 CHF), primarily due to the higher cost of PCM capsules and SHTES container materials,

Fig. 15. Stored energy in sensible (top) and hybrid (bottom) SHTES for example RBS system using daily averaged data.

which make up around 15 % of the total in the VIT configuration. This highlights the extra investment required for advanced storage technologies. Fig. 18 compares the total capital investment (CAPEX) and annual operational (OPEX) costs for the RBS concept in both system variations.

Regarding GWP contributions, considered over a 20-year lifetime for each system, the PV system is the largest contributor to GWP, accounting for 60–70 % across all systems. The Sensible RBS has the lowest GWP (90,000 CHF), while the Hybrid VIT system reaches the highest (135,000 CHF), driven by the significant environmental impact of PCM capsules and SHTES materials, which together contribute almost half of the total GWP in VIT. This reflects the increased environmental cost of using advanced storage technologies in hybrid systems.

The Sensible RBS system has the lowest OPEX (6,500 CHF/year), while the Hybrid VIT has the highest (7,500 CHF/year), largely due to higher grid electricity consumption for the heat pump. The Hybrid systems generally show about 10–15 % higher OPEX than the Sensible RBS,

Fig. 17. Summary of KPIs for comparison between fully sensible (SSTES) and hybrid (SHTES).

reflecting their added maintenance needs, calculated as a fixed percentage of the initial investment, to cover routine system checks, upkeep, and minor repairs.

3.3. Optimization

Optimization runs were conducted for each storage concept (RBS, SST, and VIT) across a range of self-sufficiency weights ($w_{SS} = 0.1$ to $w_{SS} = 0.9$), with the results revealing a clear trend: systems approaching 100 % self-sufficiency experience exponential increases in both LCOH and GWP.

As shown in Fig. 19, none of the optimized solutions, regardless of the level of self-sufficiency, were able to match the base case LCOH of 0.14 CHF/kWh. However, at lower self-sufficiency levels (around 50–60 %), systems exhibit manageable costs, with LCOH ranging between 0.2 to 0.25 CHF/kWh and GWP between 0.01 to 0.015 CHF/kWh. As the self-sufficiency target moves towards 80–100 %, LCOH and GWP increase exponentially, reaching 0.5 to 0.6 CHF/kWh for LCOH and 0.035 to 0.04 CHF/kWh for GWP. This makes high self-sufficiency levels (>90 %) financially and environmentally less viable due to the steep escalation in costs and emissions.

Fig. 20 compares the optimal solutions across the three storage concepts (RBS, SST, and VIT). The RBS system consistently performs better than the SST and VIT systems for self-sufficiency levels below 85 %, offering lower LCOH and GWP values. This advantage is attributed to the RBS system’s ability to repurpose existing basement space, requiring

Fig. 16. Sankey diagram of yearly energy flows for the SHTES RBS example.

Fig. 18. CAPEX (top), OPEX (middle) and GWP (bottom) comparison between sensible (SSTES) and hybrid (SHTES) RBS and other hybrid configurations using VIT and SST concepts.

Fig. 19. Full data-sets and identified pareto fronts on each concept

only investment in advanced insulation and waterproofing materials. At around 50 % self-sufficiency, the RBS system achieves LCOH as low as 0.2 CHF/kWh and GWP under 0.01 CHF/kWh, which is significantly lower than the SST and VIT systems that start at 0.25 CHF/kWh and show a GWP closer to 0.015 CHF/kWh.

For higher self-sufficiency levels (80 %–100 %), all systems exhibit steep increases in cost and emissions, but VIT sees the most substantial rise. The VIT system’s LCOH reaches over 0.6 CHF/kWh at 90 % self-sufficiency, while the RBS and SST systems cap at around 0.5 CHF/kWh. Similarly, GWP in the VIT system rises to 0.04 CHF/kWh, whereas RBS and SST maintain slightly lower values (0.035 CHF/kWh).

Additionally, for self-sufficiency levels below 50 %, costs remain relatively constant, with LCOH increasing only slightly (10 %–20 %) as self-sufficiency moves from 30 % to 50 %, making moderate self-sufficiency targets the most cost-effective. For these levels, GWP remains consistently low (<0.015 CHF/kWh), making the 50 %–70 % self-sufficiency range the most attractive balance between cost and environmental impact across all systems.

3.3.1. Statistical analysis of results

The statistical analysis employed a two-pronged approach: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and Spearman correlation analysis. ANOVA was utilized to discern the impact of input parameters on the designated KPIs, determining their statistical significance and highlighting pivotal

variables in system performance and optimization. Correlation analysis further scrutinized the linear interdependencies among variables, providing a quantified measure of association between each input variable and KPI, and among the KPIs themselves. To minimize collinearity, some variables such as TES dimensions considered independently during the optimization were bundled into a single volume parameter.

Table 9 summarizes the p-values obtained for the VIT concept, which reveal that key parameters such as PV peak power, HP peak power, and SHTES volume are highly statistically significant across all KPIs (SS_{th} , LCOH, and GWP), with p-values near zero. For instance, PV peak power has p-values of 0.00 E+00 for SS_{th} , 2.01 E-137 for LCOH, and 1.81 E-130 for GWP, indicating its strong influence on system performance and environmental impact. Similarly, HP peak power shows a p-value of 5.09 E-27 for SS_{th} and 0.00 E+00 for LCOH, confirming it as a key cost driver. SHTES volume also demonstrates very strong significance, with p-values of 2.59 E-40 for SS_{th} and 0.00 E+00 for both LCOH and GWP, emphasizing its critical role in balancing self-sufficiency and costs. PCM Capsule Size and PCM Relative Size, though less significant for SS_{th} (p-value of 5.18 E-01), are highly significant for LCOH (p-values of 1.94 E-46 and 6.32 E-41, respectively) and GWP (p-values of 1.73 E-04 and 7.85 E-117). This indicates their impact on system costs and emissions, especially for the VIT system where material costs and storage design become more important. In contrast, parameters like PV tilt and DHW TES volume show less influence, with higher p-values (e.g., 1.16 E-01 for LCOH for PV tilt and 6.69 E-01 for DHW TES volume), indicating

Fig. 20. Comparison of Pareto front optimal solution subsets for the three storage concepts.

Table 9

Summary of p-values for ANOVA performed on VIT full optimization dataset.

Parameter	p-SS _{th}	p-LCOH	p-GWP
PV Peak Power [kW]	0.0 E+00	2.0 E-137	1.8 E-130
PV Azimuth [deg]	5.1 E-75	1.3 E-06	1.9 E-02
PV Tilt [deg]	1.1 E-13	1.2 E-01	2.7 E-01
HP Peak Power [kW]	5.1 E-27	0.0 E+00	3.7 E-193
SHTES Vol. [m ³]	2.6 E-40	0.0 E+00	0.0 E+00
HWTES Vol. [m ³]	2.5 E-08	6.7 E-01	6.6 E-01
PCM Type [-]	2.70 E-15	8.26 E-04	8.09 E-07
PCM Rel. Size [-]	3.9 E-04	6.3 E-41	7.9 E-117
Capsule Type [-]	3.21 E-01	7.07 E-01	5.29 E-01
Capsule Size [m ³]	5.2 E-01	1.9 E-46	1.7 E-04

that while still statistically significant, they have less impact on the system's overall performance compared to the primary drivers. The results from the ANOVA for the other system configurations closely mirrored those of the VIT concept, with similar patterns of significance across parameters and KPIs. For this reason, they are not presented here, as they do not offer any additional insights beyond the results shown.

Fig. 21 presents the summarized correlation matrix for the KPIs vs influencing factors. The correlation matrices for the VIT, RBS, and SST systems show that HP Peak Power, PV Peak Power, and SHTES volume are the strongest drivers for SS_{th}, LCOH, and GWP. These parameters consistently show high correlations with both self-sufficiency and costs across all systems.

Moderate correlations (0.3–0.5) are observed for parameters like PCM capsule size and DHW tank volume, particularly for LCOH and GWP. This is largely due to Pareto front optimization, where these parameters converge to efficient ranges. For example, PCM capsule size, though important for balancing performance and cost, has been optimized early in the process, leading to smaller variations and lower observed correlations in the Pareto front. This does not imply these

Fig. 21. Summary of correlation analysis on Pareto front data sets for the three storage concepts: VIT (a), RBS (b), SST (c).

parameters are insignificant, but rather that they have already been optimized to efficient values.

Across all systems, HP Peak Power remains the dominant driver of performance, followed by PV Peak Power and SHTES volume. As costs increase (from RBS to SST and VIT), the correlation of PCM capsule size rises, reaching 0.9 in the VIT system. This reflects its increasing importance in high-cost configurations, where storage materials and technology contribute significantly to costs. In contrast, the RBS system, with its lower installation and manufacturing costs, shows reduced sensitivity to PCM size, with SHTES volume becoming more important for thermal self-sufficiency.

PCM capsule size shows a trade-off between cost and performance. Larger capsules reduce manufacturing complexity but limit power output, while smaller capsules increase LCOH and GWP due to higher production and encapsulation costs. Optimizing capsule size is crucial for balancing performance and cost, and its influence converges within the Pareto front. Additionally, a lower phase change temperature improves performance across all systems by enhancing PCM capacity utilization through more efficient charging and discharging.

The DHW tank volume plays a key role in enhancing self-sufficiency, especially when SHTES is fully charged and excess PV power is still available. Across all configurations, HWTES volume is sized to exceed daily requirements, minimizing the need for SHTES during normal operation. This allows the system to rely more on the cheaper HWTES for daily storage while reserving SHTES for peak demand or longer durations. This approach is particularly effective in the RBS system, where using repurposed basement space helps reduce both LCOH and GWP.

In summary, the convergence of certain parameters within the Pareto front explains their reduced influence in the correlation analysis, despite their importance in the overall design. While HP and PV peak power have the greatest impact on self-sufficiency and cost, parameters like PCM capsule size and DHW tank volume are carefully tuned during optimization, leading to more nuanced but essential roles.

Table 10
Summary of example optimal configurations for the three storage concepts at self-sufficiency objectives between 70 and 100 %.

SUMMARY	SST			VIT			RBS		
SS Thermal [%]	70.8	85.0	92.4	69.9	85.3	95.6	68.6	84.9	94.9
LCOH [CHF/kWh]	0.30	0.36	0.49	0.30	0.38	0.79	0.27	0.33	0.63
GWP [CHF/kWh]	0.009	0.012	0.021	0.010	0.013	0.042	0.008	0.010	0.027
SS Electric [%]	37.9	40.3	41.0	39.1	40.5	41.1	38.5	40.6	41.3
PV Self-Cons. [%]	45.7	45.3	47.8	38.6	44.3	48.3	43.4	44.8	49.6
PV [kWp]	30.4	35.3	36.1	36.1	36.1	36.1	31.5	36.1	36.1
PV [m ²]	146.0	169.7	173.3	173.3	173.3	173.3	151.4	173.3	173.3
PV Tilt [°]	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45	45
PV Azimuth [°]	180	180	180	190	180	180	190	190	190
HP Peak Power [kWe]	8.5	15.5	24.5	7.5	16.5	24.0	7.5	15.5	23.0
SHTES Vol. [m ³]	4.06	7.70	33.51	2.26	7.74	70.00	3.95	17.61	65.97
SHTES Height [m]	1.98	2.45	4.00	2.00	2.00	3.95	3.95	2.73	3.74
SHTES Diam./Width [m]	1.98	2.45	4.00	1.20	2.22	4.75	1.00	2.54	4.20
HWTES Vol. [m ³]	3.07	2.45	3.07	2.38	2.61	3.07	2.18	2.27	3.07
HWTES Height [m]	2.50	2.00	2.50	2.50	2.23	2.50	1.78	1.97	2.50
HWTES Diameter [m]	1.25	1.25	1.25	1.10	1.22	1.25	1.25	1.21	1.25
PCM Rel. Height [%]	10	80	80	45	90	90	10	10	90
PCM Rel. Vol [%]	1.5	50.1	51.5	26.1	52.1	44.2	5.1	5.7	46.1
PCM Capsule Size [L]	1.10	1.70	0.10	2.55	2.25	0.10	0.10	4.20	0.10
PCM Capsule Type [-]	CAP-4	CAP-4	CAP-4	CAP-4	CAP-4	CAP-4	CAP-1	CAP-2	CAP-2
PCM Type [-]	PCM-1								
PCM Tpc [°C]	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40	40

3.3.2. Optimal configuration samples for storage concepts

Table 10 provides a summary of KPIs and inputs for selected points for each storage concept at increasing SS_{th} , ranging from 70 % to 95.6 %. Three representative points are displayed for each concept, with the closest point to each target chosen for practical purposes. Other configurations can generate similar KPIs due to the high nonlinearity of the relationships between parameters and KPIs.

For self-sufficiency targets around 85 % or below, most parameters remain within optimized, efficient ranges, ensuring relatively moderate investment and operational costs. However, as self-sufficiency nears 100 %, systems begin to push the limits of design feasibility, such as fully utilizing PV capacity and expanding storage systems. In the VIT concept, PCM capsule usage increases to 45 % even at lower self-sufficiency levels, reflecting the competitive advantage of PCM in reducing tank investment costs. In contrast, the RBS and SST concepts maximize PCM only at very high self-sufficiency levels.

For LCOH, the RBS system consistently shows the lowest costs across most self-sufficiency levels, ranging from 0.27 CHF/kWh at 70 % self-sufficiency to 0.63 CHF/kWh at 94.9 %. SST is similarly competitive, with LCOH values between 0.30 and 0.49 CHF/kWh up to its maximum self-sufficiency of 92.4 %. While SST appears more cost-effective than RBS at these very high levels, it does not reach the same self-sufficiency target. The RBS system requires a larger storage capacity and system changes to achieve 94.9 %, driving higher costs. Meanwhile, the VIT system shows a steeper increase in costs at high self-sufficiency, reaching 0.79 CHF/kWh at 95.6 % due to its greater material and PCM requirements.

The RBS system consistently shows the lowest LCOH, ranging from 0.27 CHF/kWh at 70 % self-sufficiency to 0.63 CHF/kWh at 94.9 %. The SST system is similarly competitive, with LCOH values between 0.30 and 0.49 CHF/kWh across different self-sufficiency levels, although it achieves a slightly lower maximum self-sufficiency of 92.4 % due to a volume limit of 33 m³. This constraint stems from transportation limitations on spherical tanks, which are capped at a feasible diameter of 4 m. In contrast, the VIT system, which requires up to 70 m³ to reach comparable levels of self-sufficiency, shows a sharper increase in costs at higher self-sufficiency. Its LCOH climbs to 0.79 CHF/kWh at 95.6 %, primarily due to the cost of its steel tank design and the added use of PCM capsules, which help offset the tank's structural requirements but add to overall expenses.

Environmentally, the RBS system again shows the lowest impact, with GWP values ranging from 0.008 to 0.027 CHF/kWh. Its larger storage capacity allows it to reach high self-sufficiency with relatively less intensive material use. The SST system, constrained by the 33 m³ volume limit, has slightly higher GWP values between 0.009 and 0.021 CHF/kWh. The VIT system, however, requires extensive use of steel and PCM to achieve its higher storage capacity of 70 m³, resulting in the highest GWP among the concepts, reaching 0.042 CHF/kWh at 95.6 % self-sufficiency reflecting the embodied emissions of the materials used.

Across all systems, HP and PV systems are the dominant cost drivers. As self-sufficiency rises, HP peak power increases considerably to match higher PV output. For example, in the SST system, HP peak power grows from 8.5 kWe at 70 % self-sufficiency to 24.5 kWe at 95.6 %, reflecting the need for larger capacity systems to handle greater energy loads. Similarly, SHTES volume plays a critical role in higher self-sufficiency cases, particularly for VIT, where storage volume increases from 2.26 m³ to 70 m³ between 70 % and 95.6 % self-sufficiency.

Fig. 22 further shows that investment costs increase with self-sufficiency, with HP and PV systems consistently making up the largest portion of costs. The RBS system maintains lower storage-related costs due to its use of repurposed basement space, keeping SHTES costs minimal. The SST system experiences consistent storage costs due to manufacturer-set dimensions, while VIT shows higher storage costs as it converges toward smaller but PCM-packed tanks to balance performance and cost.

In terms of GWP contributions, as summarized in Fig. 22, PV systems are the primary contributors to total GWP across all configurations, accounting for between 60 % and 83 % of the total emissions. As self-sufficiency increases, the contribution of storage tanks and PCM materials becomes more significant, especially in the VIT system, where larger tanks and extensive PCM usage drive up GWP. The RBS system, with its more modest storage requirements, maintains the lowest GWP, reflecting its cost-effective and lower-emission design.

3.4. Study on projected scenarios

The impact of PV costs and PCM cost projections was analyzed through Pareto front optimal solutions, comparing LCOH versus SS_{th} for the RBS, SST, and VIT systems. Fig. 23(a)–(c) present the results for (a) 2019 and 2023 PV cost scenarios, (b) PCM cost and GWP projections, and (c) the combined best-case scenario for both PV and PCM costs.

Fig. 22. Summary of investment costs for example optimal configurations for the three storage concepts at self-sufficiency objectives between 70 and 100 %.

The 2023 PV cost scenario, representing current market conditions, results in 20–30 % higher LCOH across all systems compared to the 2019 projection, which is used here as a better-case scenario for future price reductions. Despite this cost increase, both the RBS and SST systems maintain competitive LCOH between 0.2 and 0.4 CHF/kWh for SS_{th} values up to 80 %, making them cost-effective options for moderate levels of thermal self-sufficiency. In contrast, the VIT system exhibits higher costs, with LCOH rising to 0.6–1.0 CHF/kWh as SS_{th} approaches 100 %, primarily due to the larger storage and material requirements. Despite the increased costs in 2023, PV remains essential for achieving high levels of self-sufficiency across all configurations. The RBS and SST systems demonstrate robust cost performance, while VIT is more sensitive to cost increases at higher self-sufficiency levels.

Projected PCM cost and GWP reductions, a 50 % decrease in PCM costs and a 30 % reduction in GWP per PCM capsule provided by COWA TS, offer substantial performance improvements across all systems. The RBS system maintains LCOH under 0.4 CHF/kWh even as SS_{th} approaches 90 %, while the SST system remains competitive, with LCOH below 0.5 CHF/kWh across most SS_{th} levels.

For the VIT system, the projected PCM improvements alleviate the sharp cost increase seen at high self-sufficiency levels, bringing LCOH down to 0.7–0.8 CHF/kWh at SS_{th} close to 100 %, a significant improvement over the current scenario. This highlights the potential for advanced PCM technologies to reduce costs and environmental impacts, particularly in high-storage systems like VIT.

In the combined best-case scenario, where both PV and PCM costs are optimized, all systems show further reductions in LCOH. The RBS system maintains LCOH under 0.4 CHF/kWh for SS_{th} up to 90 %, while the SST system remains below 0.5 CHF/kWh across the entire range of self-sufficiency levels. Even for the VIT system, which traditionally faces higher costs, LCOH remains below 0.7 CHF/kWh at SS_{th} close to 100 %, compared to the over 1.0 CHF/kWh seen in the 2023 scenario.

Between the two scenarios, storage volumes (SHTES) and PCM volumes change to maintain system performance. For the current case PCM,

Fig. 23. Comparison of PV cost functions for 2023 and 2019 for all 3 storage concepts (Left). Comparison of best-case scenario costs and GWP projection for the selected PCMs with the current state (right).

SHTES volumes grow rapidly beyond $SS_{th} = 75 %$, reaching 70 m³ at $SS_{th} = 100 %$. However, in the best-case PCM scenario, required storage volumes are reduced by 20–30 %, with many configurations requiring only 30–50 m³ for high self-sufficiency levels.

Similarly, PCM volume share within the SHTES increases to offset reductions in storage size. For SS_{th} levels between 75 % and 90 %, the PCM volume grows from 1–4 m³ in the current scenario to 6–15 m³ in the best-case projection with correspondingly smaller SHTES volumes. This balance between reducing storage volume while increasing PCM utilization highlights the role of PCM in creating more compact, cost-effective storage solutions that maintain high self-sufficiency.

The combined best-case scenario demonstrates that with optimized PV and PCM costs, even high self-sufficiency levels can be achieved at competitive costs, especially for RBS and SST, making them attractive options for achieving both economic and environmental goals.

3.5. Comparison with recent techno-economic studies

Table 11 positions our work among the most closely related techno-economic studies. Although certainly comparable, the numerical values

Table 11

Techno-economic indicators from studies most comparable to this work. Monetary figures remain in the original currencies.

Reference	Concept / size	Self-sufficiency metric	Cost metric	GWP metric	Optimization / method
[20]	Water tank, $H = 15$ m	100 % solar	LCOES ₁₀₀ 0.6 CHF/kWh–1.1 CHF/kWh	–	Diameter / insulation parametric sweep
[40]	Buried water tank (Swiss MFH)	100 % solar (ref.); PV + HP case: 50 %–70 %	CAPEX change –10 % vs. solar-only	–	Scenario study; no optimizer
[33]	PCM vs. water buffer on multi-source HP	–	CAPEX + 215 %–730 % for PCM	–	Genetic algorithm on HP + buffer sizing
[80]	Borehole TES in district heating	–	Annual cost change –6.1 %–9.8 %	CO ₂ cut 4.1 %–43.7 %	MILP optimizer
[81]	Concrete ice TES $V = 70$ m ³ –490 m ³	–	LCOE 0.087 CHF/kWh (0.087 CHF/kWh)	CO ₂ saving 15.5 %–17.5 %	MIQCP Optimization
[82]	Hybrid thermocline (sensible-rod + PCM capsules)	–	Capacity cost 35 USD/kWh–42 USD/kWh; capital 0.30 MUSD–0.62 MUSD	–	Comparative cost/performance study (no optimizer)
This work	Hybrid water + PCM in repurposed basement	SS _{th} = 70, 85, 100 %	LCOH 0.27, 0.33, 0.63 CHF/kWh	0.008, 0.010, 0.027 CHF/kWh	NOMAD multi-objective (PV, HP, TES, PCM)

Cost abbreviations: LCOE = levelized cost of energy; LCOH = levelized cost of heat; LCOES₁₀₀ = levelized cost of energy storage at 100 % solar fraction.

in the table do not correspond to the exact same aspects across the studies. Some authors adopt different functional boundaries, currencies, discount rates and, most importantly, different key-performance indicators. For example, the widely used levelized cost of energy (LCOE) includes every unit of energy exported by a plant over its lifetime, whereas the levelized cost of heat (LCOH) employed here is restricted to useful heat delivered to the building; PV electricity and the heat-pump input are still counted in the cost numerator, but the denominator is heat alone. Villasmil [20] introduced the storage-specific indicator LCOES₁₀₀ [CHF/kWh], defined at a forced solar fraction of 100 %; by construction that metric excludes the solar collectors themselves and cannot be equated with whole-system LCOE or LCOH figures. Some scenario studies such as Ruesch [40] report percentage changes in the bare capital expenditure, relative to a reference case; without annuitization or an energy denominator those values serve only as qualitative pointers. A further complication is the diversity of optimization targets: one study tunes surface-to-volume ratios, another minimizes greenhouse-gas emissions per unit of district-heating demand, yet another focuses on control strategy or partial-load behavior.

Even within the heterogeneous KPI landscape of Table 11 a few quantitative anchors emerge. Villasmil et al. [20] storage-specific LCOES₁₀₀ = 0.6–1.1 CHF kWh⁻¹ exceeds our LCOH = 0.63 CHF kWh⁻¹ at a similar degree of self-sufficiency SS_{th} = 94.9 %, highlighting the cost leverage of a repurposed basement. At intermediate autonomy Ruesch et al. [40] reports a ~ 10 % CAPEX saving when PV and HP are added to an all-water store; our 70 % case attains a comparable cost level (0.27 CHF kWh⁻¹) while cutting the monetized GWP to 8×10^{-3} CHF kWh⁻¹. On climate metrics the 4–44 % CO₂ reduction achieved by district-scale BTES [80] is matched by a 75 % cut for the building-scale hybrid system presented here. Normalizing for heat-only output, Vivian et al. [81] ice storage (LCOE = 0.087 CHF kWh⁻¹, 15–18 % CO₂ saving) converges on our 70 % design, suggesting that sensible-latent are of practical interest.

Consequently, the apparent gaps in Table 11 should be read as orders of magnitude and directional trends rather than as a numerical league table. Still, three robust messages emerge. First, sensible-latent hybridization can narrow the cost penalty traditionally associated with high-solar-fraction tanks. Second, repurposed-volume concepts such as our basement storage (RBS) offer a qualitatively different route to cost control than heavily engineered vacuum or double-steel vessels. Third, only a handful of earlier publications report cost, autonomy and life-cycle environmental impact figures within the same optimization loop. By presenting LCOH, GWP and SS_{th} on a common Pareto frontier the present study therefore complements previous single-objective results. Looking ahead, the community would profit

from harmonized KPI definitions and fully transparent system boundaries so that seasonal-storage concepts can be bench marked on equal footing.

4. Conclusions

This study presents a detailed model for a Seasonal Hybrid Thermal Energy Storage (SHTES) system, integrating sensible heat storage in water with latent storage through encapsulated Phase Change Materials (PCMs). The model captures key processes such as thermal stratification in the sensible storage and phase change dynamics of the PCM capsules, while also incorporating photovoltaic (PV) panels and an air-source heat pump (HP). This model is applied in a comprehensive multi-objective optimization to explore the trade-offs between thermal self-sufficiency (SS_{th}), Levelized Cost of Heat (LCOH), and Global Warming Potential (GWP) for a multi-family building, identifying configurations that achieve an optimal balance between economic and environmental performance.

The optimization revealed that no single solution optimally balances cost, self-sufficiency, and GWP across all scenarios. However, the optimal configurations show that systems achieving around 70 % thermal self-sufficiency provide the most balanced results. At this level, the LCOH remains between 0.2–0.3 CHF/kWh, while GWP is reduced to 0.01–0.015 CHF/kWh. The Repurposed Basement Storage (RBS) concept is particularly effective at moderate self-sufficiency levels, with storage volumes as low as 8 m³ achieving SS_{th} up to 85 % with reasonable costs. Beyond this, both costs and storage volumes increase exponentially, with diminishing returns for higher self-sufficiency. For self-sufficiency levels below 70 %, the system offers comparable costs to traditional solutions but significantly reduces GWP compared to an oil boiler, making it an environmentally superior alternative.

Example results of analog systems with consistent tank volume demonstrate the enhanced performance of hybrid storage systems, showing more stable temperature profiles and increased energy storage capacity during periods of high demand compared to sensible-only systems. These findings highlight the model's capability in capturing critical system dynamics, supporting its use for optimizing performance and cost trade-offs.

Analysis of the optimization data confirms that PV peak power, HP capacity, and SHTES capacity are the most significant cost and performance drivers, with p-values near zero across key performance indicators (KPIs). The Pareto fronts clearly show that beyond 70 % self-sufficiency, the trade-offs become steeper, with LCOH rising to over 0.6 CHF/kWh and GWP increasing to 0.035–0.04 CHF/kWh as self-sufficiency approaches 100 %. Among the configurations, the

Repurposed Basement Storage (RBS) system maintains the lowest costs and GWP, primarily because it reuses existing space, requiring less material for construction and insulation. In comparison, the Spherical Storage Tank (SST) performs competitively, but its volume is limited by transport constraints, impacting its scalability for higher self-sufficiency. The Vacuum Insulated Tank (VIT) system sees the most notable rise in both LCOH and GWP due to the need for a double-layered steel structure and extensive PCM to reach similar self-sufficiency levels, both of which drive up embodied emissions and costs.

Future cost reductions in PCM technologies and projected increases in CO₂ prices could further enhance the economic viability of TES. The projected 50 % decrease in PCM costs and 30 % reduction in PCM-related GWP would make the hybrid system more competitive, particularly for SS_{th} in the 75–90 %. Under these cost-reduction scenarios, the LCOH of the RBS system lowers to around 0.23 CHF/kWh and the GWP to 21 % for SS_{th} around 70 %. Additionally, the costs remain below 0.4 CHF/kWh even at high self-sufficiency, and the VIT system's LCOH drops to 0.7 CHF/kWh at 95 % SS_{th}, compared to over 1.0 CHF/kWh in current market conditions.

Higher carbon pricing would make sustainable, low-carbon systems like TES more competitive relative to fossil fuel alternatives, amplifying their environmental and economic benefits. Despite TES being a significant cost driver in sustainable energy systems, it is not the dominant factor. Instead, PV and HP infrastructure constitute the largest portions of both cost and environmental impact in these systems. Reframing TES from a cost-center to a vital component in achieving higher self-sufficiency and resilience shifts the focus towards its long-term value in decarbonization efforts. While investments in TES are essential, they remain secondary to the costs associated with energy production (PV) and energy conversion (HP), both of which heavily influence overall system costs and emissions. Therefore, even as we pursue advancements in PV and HP technology, targeted investments in TES could play an increasingly strategic role in balancing performance with sustainability goals.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

William Delgado-Díaz: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal

analysis, Conceptualization. **Willy Villasmil:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Marcel Troxler:** Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Ruben Hijwegen:** Methodology, Investigation. **Reto Hendry:** Validation, Resources, Investigation. **Ueli Schilt:** Writing – review & editing, Software, Resources, Conceptualization. **Philipp Roos:** Validation, Resources, Methodology. **Rebecca Ravotti:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Anastasia Stamatou:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration. **Sophia Haussener:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources. **Jörg Worlitschek:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the author(s) used ChatGPT in order to improve readability and language of the work. After using this tool/service, the author(s) reviewed and edited the content as needed and take(s) full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests.

Jörg Worlitschek reports financial support was provided by Swiss Federal Office of Energy. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This research was funded by the Swiss Federal Office of Energy (SFOE) through project “HyTES - Optimierung Hybrider Saisonalener Wärmespeichersysteme mithilfe von Phasenwechselmaterialien” (Grant Nr. SI/502171) and as part of the SWEET consortium PATHFNDR (Grant Nr. SI/502259). We acknowledge the valuable contributions of our partners, Cowa Thermal Solutions AG and Planergie AG, for their expertise and support.

A. Appendix

Table 12
Cost functions for each component of the hybrid system.

Component	Cost Function (CHF)	Description	Reference
PV System	$I_{PV} = \begin{cases} 12072 + 1646 \cdot PV_{kWp}, & PV_{kWp} < 30 \\ 22241 + 1307 \cdot PV_{kWp}, & 30 \leq PV_{kWp} < 100 \\ 42753 + 1102 \cdot PV_{kWp}, & PV_{kWp} \geq 100 \end{cases}$	Investment cost of PV system based on peak power installed (CHF/kWp)	[64]
Heat Pump	$I_{HP} = 1167 \cdot HP_{kWth} + 19618$	Cost function for the heat pump system, linear based on thermal capacity (CHF)	[24,40,66,67,69]
PCM Capsules	$I_{PCM} = C_{PCM} \cdot m_{PCM} + C_{mix} \cdot V_{PCM} + C_{cap} \cdot m_{cap} + n_{caps} \cdot (C_{prod} + C_{fill})$	Cost function for PCM capsules, including PCM material, mixing, capsule material, production, and filling costs (CHF)	COWA
SHTES (VIT)	$I_{SHTES} = 7427.4 \cdot V_{TES}^{0.5038}$	Cost function for vacuum insulated tank (VIT) storage, based on total volume (m ³)	[20]
SHTES (RBS)	$I_{SHTES} = (487.37 \cdot isl_{thickness} + 39.19) \cdot A_{TES}$	Cost function for repurposed basement storage (RBS), based on surface area (m ²) and insulation thickness	[57]
SHTES (SST)	$I_{SHTES} = (0.0008 \cdot V_{TES}^4) - (0.219 \cdot V_{TES}^3) + (20.383 \cdot V_{TES}^2) - (62.813 \cdot V_{TES}) + 17630$	Cost function for spherical storage tank (SST) based on storage volume (m ³)	Planergie AG
HWTES	$I_{HWTES} = 798.18 \cdot V_{DHW} + 1035.9$	Cost function for domestic hot water tanks based on volume (CHF)	[20]
Excavation Costs	$I_{Exc} = -0.0601 \cdot V_{TES}^2 + 89.341 \cdot V_{TES} + 2202.8$	Excavation cost function based on total TES volume (CHF)	[20]

Table 13
GWP contributions for each component of the hybrid system.

Component	GWP Function (kg CO ₂ -eq)	Description	Reference
PV System	$GWP_{PV} = 1116.9 \times PV_{elPeakPower} \times PV_{nPanels}$	GWP for Mono-Si PV modules calculated per kWp installed. Uses a factor of 1116.9 kg CO ₂ -eq/kWp for Mono-Si modules.	[58,59,71,72]
Heat Pump	$GWP_{HP} = 4.891 \times (HP_{kWth})^2 - 31.36 \times HP_{kWth} + 3039.83$	Quadratic function for air-source heat pump GWP based on thermal capacity (kWth).	[16–18,39,73,83]
HWTES	$GWP_{HWTES} = 8.556 \times (109.89 \times V_{tot} + 65.196)$	GWP for a domestic hot water tank estimating the weight based on volume.	[20,74,84]
SHTES (VIT)	$GWP_{SHTES} = 2 \times (8.556) \times (109.89 \times V_{tot} + 65.196)$	GWP based on tank volume (m ³) using a linear relationship for the storage tank's mass, multiplied by a factor of 2 to account for the double envelope.	[20,74,84]
SHTES (RBS)	$GWP_{SHTES} = \text{Surface Area} \times 303.56 \times \text{Insulation Thickness}$	GWP based on the tank's surface area and insulation thickness (0.23 m), with a GWP factor of 303.56 kg CO ₂ -eq/m ³ for the insulation material (XPS).	[75]
SHTES (SST)	$GWP_{SHTES} = (\text{GFRP Volume} \times 970.4) + (\text{PUR Volume} \times 541.27)$	GWP for a storage tank made from glass-fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) and polyurethane (PUR) insulation, based on their respective volumes.	[56,76,85,86]
PCM Capsules	$GWP_{PCM} = \text{Capsule Volume} \times 3614.81 \times \text{Number of Capsules}$	GWP for PCM capsules, with a GWP factor of 3614.81 kg CO ₂ -eq per m ³ of PCM.	COWA
Grid Electricity (Operational)	$GWP_{E_{Grid}} = E_{Grid} \times 0.128$	GWP for grid electricity consumption based on the Swiss grid mix average of 0.128 kg CO ₂ -eq/kWh.	[72]

Table 14
Key reference studies screened for this work.

Reference	Storage concept	Medium, scale / geometry	Primary aim / KPI
[21]	Tank STES	Water, <i>H</i> = 15 m cylinder	100 % solar fraction; control-strategy study
[20]	Tank STES	Water, <i>H</i> = 15 m cylinder	LCOE sensitivity to insulation detail
[22]	Pit + tank STES	Water, 7 GWh pit	Annual efficiency; model validation
[82]	Thermocline	Oil + brick/PCM, <i>H</i> = 7.5 m	CFD discharge; effective efficiency
[7]	Domestic tank	Water + macro-PCM	CFD stratification correlations
[80]	BTES	Soil, 50–200 GWh	District-heating CO ₂ mitigation
[81]	Ice tank STES	Ice-water, 70–490 m ³	LCOE, CO ₂ , insulation trade-off
[8]	Review	-	Techno-economic synthesis of STES
[35]	Hybrid steam + PCM	Steam 265 m ³ + PCM	Retrofit cost analysis
[30]	Shell-and-tube	Oil + HDPE PCM, 20 kWh	Prototype test, 55 kW peak
[6]	DHW tank hybrid	Water + salt-hydrate PCM, 49 L	+10 % delivered energy
[34]	Modular PCM tank	PCM 56 kWh, single-family	Tank efficiency 90 %
[33]	Buffer (water vs. PCM)	0.3–1.0 m ³	GA optimization, SCOP & CAPEX
[40]	Tank STES + HP	Water, multi-family	Volume –30 % with PV + HP
[32]	Micro-heat-pipe array	PCM modules, 42 mm height	+16 % charge power
[4]	Vacuum HW tank	12 m ³ , VIP insulation	Auxiliary saving 14–17 MWh a ⁻¹
[30]	Tube-bundle hybrid	Oil + HDPE PCM	80 % latent share; model error < 5 %
[80]	BTES + solar	Boreholes 6–65 °C	CO ₂ cut up to 44 %
[81]	Ice STES (variant)	490 m ³	LCOE 0.087 CHF kWh ⁻¹

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

[1] Xu J, Wang RZ, Li Y. A review of available technologies for seasonal thermal energy storage. *Sol Energy* 2014;103:610–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2013.06.006>

[2] Alva G, Lin Y, Fang G. An overview of thermal energy storage systems. *Energy* 2018;144:341–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.12.037>

[3] IRENA. Innovation outlook: thermal energy storage; 2020. <https://www.irena.org/publications/2020/Nov/Innovation-outlook-Thermal-energy-storage>

[4] Gerschitzka M, Lang S, Rieder M, Sirch M, Marx R, Bauer D, et al. Entwicklung großvolumiger, preiswerter Warmwasserspeicher mit hocheffizienter Dämmung zur Außenaufstellung. 2016:157.

[5] Stropnik R, Koželj R, Zavrli E, Stritih U. Improved thermal energy storage for nearly zero energy buildings with PCM integration. *Sol Energy* 2019;190:420–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.08.041>

[6] Frazzica A, Manzan M, Sapienza A, Freni A, Toniato G, Restuccia G. Experimental testing of a hybrid sensible-latent heat storage system for domestic hot water applications. *Appl Energy* 2016;183:1157–67. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.09.076>

[7] Pabst V, Mengedocht G, Renze P. A comparison of stratified heat storage with and without modular PCM storage through simulation. 2019:1–12. <https://doi.org/10.18086/eurosun2018.11.01>

[8] Yang T, Liu W, Kramer GJ, Sun Q. Seasonal thermal energy storage: a techno-economic literature review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2021;139(December 2020):110732. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.110732>

[9] Tronchin L, Manfren M, Nastasi B. Energy efficiency, demand side management and energy storage technologies – a critical analysis of possible paths of integration in the built environment. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2018;95(November):341–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2018.06.060>

[10] Child M, Bogdanov D, Breyer C. The role of storage technologies for the transition to a 100 % renewable energy system in Europe. In: *Energy Procedia*; vol. 155. Elsevier B.V.; 2018. p. 44–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egypro.2018.11.067>

[11] Schuetz P, Gwerder D, Gasser L, Wellig B, Worlitschek J. Thermal storage facilitates higher flexibility in smart grids for residential heating systems with heat pump. In: 4th SCCER Symposium Heat and Electricity Storage; 2016.

[12] Hewicker Christian, Werner Oliver RJ, Michael E, Tim DM, Nynke DV. Energiespeicher in der Schweiz / Bedarf, Wirtschaftlichkeit und Rahmenbedingungen im Kontext der Energiestrategie 2050, Tech. Rep. BFE; 2013.

[13] FOEN. Switzerland's greenhouse gas inventory 1990-2015, National Inventory Report 2017. Swiss Federal Office For The Environment 2017 April.

[14] Zuberi MJS, Narula K, Klinke S, Chambers J, Streicher KN, Patel MK. Potential and costs of decentralized heat pumps and thermal networks in Swiss residential areas. *Int J Energy Res* 2021;45(10):15245–64. <https://doi.org/10.1002/er.6801>

[15] Bundesamt für Energie BFE. Energieperspektiven 2050+, Kurzbericht, Tech. Rep. 2020 November. <https://www.bfe.admin.ch/bfe/de/home/politik/energieperspektiven-2050-plus.html>

[16] Carbotech, Commissioned by SFOE. Life cycle inventories of heating systems – Switzerland (February) (2021). <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/dam/bafu/en/dokumente/wirtschaft-konsum/externe-studien-berichte/life-cycle-inventories-of-heating.pdf.download.pdf/life-cycle-inventories-of-heating.pdf>

[17] Greening B, Azapagic A. Domestic heat pumps: life cycle environmental impacts and potential implications for the UK. *Energy* 2012;39(1):205–17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2012.01.028>

- [18] Smith M, Bevacqua A, Tembe S, Lal P. Life cycle analysis (LCA) of residential ground source heat pump systems: a comparative analysis of energy efficiency in New Jersey. *Sustain Energy Technol Assess* 2021;47(May):101364. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seta.2021.101364>
- [19] Sadeghi G. Energy storage on demand: thermal energy storage development, materials, design, and integration challenges. *Energy Storage Mater* 2022;46:192–222. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ensm.2022.01.017>
- [20] Villasmil W, Troxler M, Hendry R, Worlitschek J. OPTSAIS – exergetic and economic optimization of seasonal thermal energy storage systems; 2019. <https://www.aramis.admin.ch/Default?DocumentID=62816&Load=true>
- [21] Villasmil W, Troxler M, Hendry R, Schuetz P, Worlitschek J. Control strategies of solar heating systems coupled with seasonal thermal energy storage in self-sufficient buildings. *J Energy Storage* 2021;42:103069. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2021.103069>. <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S2352152X21007775>
- [22] Narula K, de Oliveira Filho F, Villasmil W, Patel MK. Simulation method for assessing hourly energy flows in district heating system with seasonal thermal energy storage. *Renew Energy* 2020;151:1250–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2019.11.121>
- [23] Fais B, Blesl M. Integrating policy instruments into energy system models-from theory to application to Germany. 2015. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-16540-0_7, Vol. 30. <http://www.scopus.com/inward/record.url?eid=2-s2.0-84928237452&partnerID=tzOtx3y1>
- [24] Berger M, Schroeteler B, Sperle H, Püntener P, Felder T, Worlitschek J. Assessment of residential scale renewable heating solutions with thermal energy storages. *Energy* 2022;244:122618. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2021.122618>
- [25] Majumdar R, Saha SK. Effect of varying extent of PCM capsule filling on thermal stratification performance of a storage tank. *Energy* 2019;178:1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENERGY.2019.04.101>
- [26] Sharma A, Tyagi VV, Chen CR, Buddhi D. Review on thermal energy storage with phase change materials and applications. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2009;13(2):318–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2007.10.005>
- [27] Teamah HM, Lightstone MF, Cotton JS. An alternative approach for assessing the benefit of phase change materials in solar domestic hot water systems. *Sol Energy* 2017;158(August):875–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.10.033>. <https://ac.els-cdn.com/S0038092X17309039/1-s2.0-S0038092X17309039-main.pdf?tid=d133af76-c945-11e7-b815-00000aacb362&acdnat=1510668915180528abc0fa7ee01d33261dfbe0515>
- [28] Ma Z, Bao H, Roskilly AP. Study on solidification process of sodium acetate trihydrate for seasonal solar thermal energy storage. *Sol Energy Mater Sol Cells* 2017;172(July):99–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solmat.2017.07.024>
- [29] Zhou G, Xiang Y. Experimental investigations on stable supercooling performance of sodium acetate trihydrate PCM for thermal storage. *Sol Energy* 2017;155:1261–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2017.07.073>
- [30] Zauner C, Hengstberger F, Mörzinger B, Hofmann R, Walter H. Experimental characterization and simulation of a hybrid sensible-latent heat storage. *Appl Energy* 2017;189:506–19. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.12.079>
- [31] Ahmed N, Elfeky KE, Qaisrani MA, Wang QW. Numerical characterization of thermocline behaviour of combined sensible-latent heat storage tank using brick manganese rod structure impregnated with PCM capsules. *Sol Energy* 2019;180(December 2018):243–56. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.01.001>
- [32] Wang Y, Quan Z, Zhao Y, Wang L, Wang Q. Multi-objective optimization of a novel phase-change thermal storage unit based on theoretical modeling and genetic algorithm. *Appl Therm Eng* 2024 February;252:123677. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2024.123677>
- [33] Pelella F, Zsembinski G, Viscito L, William Mauro A, Cabeza LF. Thermo-economic optimization of a multi-source (air/sun/ground) residential heat pump with a water/PCM thermal storage. *Appl Energy* 2023;331:120398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2022.120398> (September 2022).
- [34] Bianco N, Fragnito A, Iasiello M, Mauro GM. Multiscale analysis of a seasonal latent thermal energy storage with solar collectors for a single-family building. *Therm Sci Eng Prog* 2024 March;50:102538. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tsep.2024.102538>
- [35] Hofmann R, Dusek S, Gruber S, Drexler-Schmid G. Design optimization of a hybrid steam-PCM thermal energy storage for industrial applications. *Energies* 2019;12(5):1–25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12050898>
- [36] Del Amo A, Martínez-Gracia A, Pintanel T, Bayod-Rújula AA, Torné S. Analysis and optimization of a heat pump system coupled to an installation of PVT panels and a seasonal storage tank on an educational building. *Energy Build* 2020;226:110373. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110373>
- [37] Becattini V, Geissbühler L, Zanganeh G, Haselbacher A, Steinfeld A. Pilot-scale demonstration of advanced adiabatic compressed air energy storage, part 2: tests with combined sensible/latent thermal-energy storage. *J Energy Storage* 2018;17:140–52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2018.02.003>
- [38] Guelpa E, Verda V. Thermal energy storage in district heating and cooling systems: a review. 2019 oct;252. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2019.113474>
- [39] Li G. Comprehensive investigations of life cycle climate performance of packaged air source heat pumps for residential application. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2015;43:702–10. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.11.078>
- [40] Ruesch F, Lichtensteiger F, Bataglia M, Haller M, Villasmil W, Ammann S, et al. SensOpt – Sensible saisonale Wärmespeicherung optimal eingesetzt für die vollständig solare Beheizung von Mehrfamilienhäusern. Weiterentwicklung des Jenni-Aktivhauses in Bezug auf Raum- und Kosteneffizienz, Tech. rep., Rapperswil, Switzerland: SPF Institut für Solartechnik OST – Ostschweizer Fachhochschule und Hochschule Luzern – Technik und Architektur, CCTES Competence Center Thermal Energy Storage; 2022. <https://www.bfe.admin.ch>
- [41] Audet C, Digabel SL, Montplaisir VR, Tribes C. NOMAD version 4: nonlinear optimization with the MADS algorithm. (2021 apr). [arXiv:2104.11627](https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.11627). <https://arxiv.org/abs/2104.11627>
- [42] Márquez JMA, Bohórquez MÁM, Melgar SG. Ground thermal diffusivity calculation by direct soil temperature measurement. application to very low enthalpy geothermal energy systems. *Sensors (Switzerland)* 2016;16(3). <https://doi.org/10.3390/s16030306>
- [43] Ashour SK, Abdel-Hameed MA. Approximate skew normal distribution. *J Adv Res* 2010;1(4):341–50. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jare.2010.06.004>
- [44] Grabo M, Acar E, Kenig EY. Modeling and improvement of a packed bed latent heat storage filled with non-spherical encapsulated PCM-Elements. *Renew Energy* 2021;173:1087–97. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.04.022>
- [45] Bellini A, Bifaretti S, Iacovone V, Cornaro C. Simplified model of a photovoltaic module. In: 2009 Applied electronics international conference, AE 2009; (October) 2009. p. 47–52
- [46] Migan G-A. Project report 2013 MVK160 heat and Mass transfer study of the operating temperature of a PV module. 2013.
- [47] Perez R, Seals R, Ineichen P, Stewart R, Menicucci D. A new simplified version of the Perez diffuse irradiance model for tilted surfaces. *Sol Energy* 1987;39(3):221–31. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X\(87\)80031-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0038-092X(87)80031-2)
- [48] NOAA ESRL Global Monitoring Laboratory. <https://gml.noaa.gov/>
- [49] PV*SOL – Valentin Software. <https://valentin-software.com/produkte/pvsol/>
- [50] Mitsubishi. Wärmepumpenprogramm Lösungen für Wärme- und Trinkwarmwasserversorgung. 2024.
- [51] Meteororm Zeitreihen - Meteororm (de). <https://meteororm.com/meteororm-zeitreihen>
- [52] SIA 385/1 (2020) Anlagen für Trinkwarmwasser in Gebäuden - Grundlagen und Anforderungen Referenznummer; 2020. file:///C:/Users/FabianBarnet/Normen/sia/Disk/385-1_2011_AnlagenfürTrinkwarmwasserinGebäuden_mitKorrigenda_2013.pdf
- [53] Jordan U, Vajen K. DHWcalc. 2003.
- [54] Tjaden T, Joseph B, Quaschnig V. Repräsentative elektrische Lastprofile für Wohngebäude in Deutschland auf 1-sekundiger Datenbasis. HTW Berlin 2015;(November):8.
- [55] EnergieSchweiz. Faktenblatt: Stromverbrauch eines typischen Haushalts. 2021 August) 1–3.
- [56] Energy4me. enerSAFE Warmwasserspeicher; 2022). <https://www.energy4me.ch/speicherloesung/>
- [57] swisspor Management AG, Hochschule Luzern. Innosuisse Projekt “GEAS” (Projekt-Nr. 27954.1 PFIW-IW). 2019.
- [58] Frischknecht R, Stolz P, Krebs L, de Wild-Scholten M, Sinha P, Fthenakis V, et al. Life cycle inventories and life cycle assessments of photovoltaic systems 2020. 2020 June.
- [59] Cucchiella F, Dadaio I. Estimation of the energetic and environmental impacts of a roof-mounted building-integrated photovoltaic systems. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2012;16(7):5245–59. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2012.04.034>
- [60] Grodzewich O, Romanko O. Normalization and other topics in multi-objective optimization. Proceedings of the Fields-MITACS Industrial Problems Workshop 2006;2(August 2006):89–101. <https://www.academia.edu/11635242>
- [61] Anderegg D, Strebel S, Rohrer J. Photovoltaik Potenzial auf Dachflächen in der Schweiz. *Zhaw* 2022.
- [62] Suntech. IEC-STP-Ultra-Smini-NO₂-02-rev2021. 2021.
- [63] Partopour B, Dixon AG. An integrated workflow for resolved-particle packed bed models with complex particle shapes. *Powder Technol* 2017;322:258–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2017.09.009>
- [64] Bundesamt E, Pulverstrasse EFFE, Postadresse I, Infoline B. Photovoltaikmarkt: Preisbeobachtungsstudie 2022. 2023.
- [65] Sauter Y, Jacqmin F. Photovoltaikmarkt- Beobachtungsstudie 2019. 2020.
- [66] Stiebel Eltron. Preisliste PL 38 2020. 2020.
- [67] CTA AG. Preisliste 2021: Wärmepumpen-Systeme der CTA AG, accessed from <cta.ch/wp-unterlagen> (Jun. 2021). <http://www.cta.ch/wp-unterlagen>
- [68] Institut für Gebäudetechnik und Energie (IGE), Hochschule Luzern. IGE Vergleichsrechner. 2021.
- [69] Centralschweizerische Kraftwerke AG. CKW Heizungsrechner, <https://heizungsrechner.ckw.ch/ckw/#/df/start>, accessed: [2021-08-25].
- [70] Carnie JT, Hardalupas Y, Sergis A. Decarbonising building heating and cooling: designing a novel, inter-seasonal latent heat storage system. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 2024;189(PA):113897. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2023.113897>
- [71] Fthenakis VM, Kim HC. Photovoltaics: life-cycle analyses. *Sol Energy* 2011;85(8):1609–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2009.10.002>
- [72] Krebs L, Frischknecht R. Umweltbilanz Strommixe Schweiz 2018, im Auftrag des Bundesamtes für Umwelt (BAFU), 27. April 2021. p. 1–53 (April) (2021). <https://www.bafu.admin.ch/bafu/en/home/topics/climate/questions-answers.html#2097182071>
- [73] Johnson EP. Air-source heat pump carbon footprints: HFC impacts and comparison to other heat sources. *Energy Policy* 2011;39(3):1369–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2010.12.009>
- [74] GmbH S-T-TS. Wärme lange speichern im Sirch vacuotherm. 2013.
- [75] Frischknecht R. UMWELTPRODUKTDEKLARATION NACH NORM SN EN 15804+A1:2013: swissporXPS, Wärmedämmplatten aus extrudiertem Polystyrol. 2017:1–7 (November 2017).
- [76] Plastic GR. ENVIRONMENTAL PRODUCT Glassfiber Reinforced Plastic (GRP) pipes. 2021.
- [77] Spearman rank correlation coefficient. New York, NY: Springer New York; 2008. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-32833-1_379
- [78] van Dronkelaar C, Dowson M, Spataru C, Burman E, Mumovic D. Quantifying the underlying causes of a discrepancy between predicted and measured energy use. *Front Mech Eng* 2019 May;5:1–14. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmech.2019.00020>

- [79] Chen C, Gao Z, Zhou X, Wang M, Yan J, Gao Z, et al. Energy consumption prediction and energy-saving suggestions of public buildings based on machine learning. *Energy Build* 2024 March;320:114585. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2024.114585>
- [80] Fiorentini M, Heer P, Baldini L. Design optimization of a district heating and cooling system with a borehole seasonal thermal energy storage. *Energy* 2023;262(PB):125464. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.125464>
- [81] Vivian J, Heer P, Fiorentini M. Optimal sizing and operation of seasonal ice thermal storage systems. *Energy Build* 2023 October;300:113633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.113633>
- [82] Ahmed N, Elfeky KE, Lu L, Wang QW. Thermal and economic evaluation of thermocline combined sensible-latent heat thermal energy storage system for medium temperature applications. *Energy Convers Manag* 2019 March;189:14–23. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2019.03.040>
- [83] Bonn S. Aktualisierte Umweltekklärung 2019. 2019.
- [84] GmbH S-T-TS. Speicher Anfragen-Konfigurator. <https://pufferspeicher-sirch.de/speicher/anfragen-konfigurator/>
- [85] Abbood IS, Odaa SA, Hasan KF, Jasim MA. Properties evaluation of fiber reinforced polymers and their constituent materials used in structures - a review. *Mater Today: Proc* 2021;43:1003–08. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2020.07.636>
- [86] Epd, International. Environmental product declaration - polyurethane thermal insulation spray foam (Cem Iii) (1–14); 2017. <http://www.brick.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2014/01/Please-click-here-to-download-the-EDP.pdf>